

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

DIGITAL HUMANITIES 2023

DH 2023

Collaboration
as Opportunity

ALLIANCE OF
DIGITAL
HUMANITIES
ORGANIZATIONS

Digital Humanities 2023: Book of Abstracts

Editors

Anne Baillot, Le Mans Université, ORCID: 0000-0002-4593-059X

Walter Scholger, University of Graz, ORCID: 0000-0002-9256-0958

Toma Tasovac, Belgrade Center for Digital Humanities, ORCID: 0000-0002-3919-993X

Georg Vogeler, University of Graz, ORCID: 0000-0002-1726-1712

Data Management

Elisabeth Raunig, University of Graz, ORCID: 0009-0007-9019-8215

Martina Scholger, University of Graz, ORCID: 0000-0003-1438-3236

Elisabeth Steiner, University of Graz, ORCID: 0000-0001-9116-0402

Publisher

Zentrum für Informationsmodellierung - Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities,
University of Graz

Citation Recommendation

Baillot, Anne / Scholger, Walter / Tasovac, Toma / Vogeler, Georg / Raunig, Elisabeth /
Scholger, Martina / Steiner, Elisabeth (eds.). Digital Humanities 2023: Book of Abstracts.
Graz 2023. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7961822

<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

CENTRE FOR
INFORMATION-MODELLING
AUSTRIAN CENTRE FOR
DIGITAL HUMANITIES

Table of Contents

Keynotes

Two-Fold Revolutions: Computational Museology in the Age of Experience <i>Kenderdine, Sarah</i>	22
Contesting power in the digital age: the role of civil society in Europe <i>Fernandez, Claire</i>	23

Workshops

ADHO Community Forum: Transparency, Trust, Engagement, Diversity <i>Layne-Worthey, Glen; Jakacki, Diane; Brown, Susan; Schöch, Christof</i>	25
A Model for Modeling Problems - Game Design as an Exercise in Formal Abstraction <i>Pielström, Steffen; Wintjes, Jorit</i>	25
Amplifying unheard voices in Digital Humanities: an OpenMethods edit-a-thon <i>Tóth-Czifra, Erzsébet; Wuttke, Ulrike; Horváth, Alíz; Nunn, Christopher</i>	26
An introduction to Transkribus: how to use Handwritten Text Recognition in research and teaching <i>Mansutti, Sara</i>	28
AudiAnnotate Workshop with Radio Venceremos, Rebel Radio Station and SpokenWeb: Using IIIF with AV to Build Editions and Exhibits. <i>Clement, Tanya; Bursztajn-Illingworth, Zoe; Wintermeier, Trent; Burrows, Vera</i>	29
Creating a DH workflow in the SSH Open Marketplace <i>Barbot, Laure; Battaner Moro, Elena; Buddenbohm, Stefan; Concordia, Cesare; Dolinar, Maja; Đurčo, Matej; Gray, Edward; Grisot, Cristina; Illmayer, Klaus; Kirnbauer, Martin; Kleemola, Mari; König, Alexander; Kurzmeier, Michael; McGillivray, Barbara; Parente Boavida, Clara; Schuster, Christian; Vipavc Brvar, Irena; Wnuk, Magdalena</i>	31
Creating, storing, and sharing your own web archives with open source Webrecorder tools <i>Mulliken, Jasmine Tiffany; Kreymer, Ilya</i>	33
DH4MA - (Digital Humanities for Marginal Areas). Tangible and Intangible heritage digitalization to promote marginal areas and rural development <i>Pascucci, Antonio; Carlino, Carola; Monti, Johanna; Manna, Raffaele</i>	35
Digital Humanities Applications of spaCy's Span Categorizer <i>Boyd, Adriane; Kádár, Ákos; Janco, Andrew; Lassner, David; Budak, Nick; Tasovac, Toma; Ermolaev, Natalia; Karajgikar, Jajwalya</i>	36
Digital Pathways Through Newspaper Advertisements: Workflows from Printed Page to Digital Analysis with the Avisblatt-R-Package <i>Dickmann, Lars; Reimann, Anna; Serif, Ina</i>	38
Drafting Standards for Stylometry <i>Juola, Patrick; Byszuk, Joanna</i>	40
Frameworks for User-Focused Digital Humanities Projects: Half-day workshop proposal <i>Mapp, Rennie; Wandl-Vogt, Eveline; Theron, Roberto</i>	42
From Sketching to Coding: Visualization as a Thinking Process <i>Hinrichs, Uta; Windhager, Florian; El-Assady, Mennatallah; Alexander, Eric; Bradley, Adam; Bludau, Mark-Jan</i>	43
How can you trust your code? <i>Damerow, Julia; Vogl, Malte; Koeser, Rebecca Sutton; Casties, Robert</i>	45
Labs for Labs: a participatory workshop on digital lab practices in the humanities and social sciences <i>Kelly, Aodhán; Ciula, Arianna; Ferraro, Ginestra; Frissen, Thom; Papadopoulos, Costas; Rasterhoff, Claartje; Mellen, Pamela; Noël, Geoffroy</i>	45
LEAF: Developing Streamlined Digital Scholarly Workflows with the Linked Editing Academic Framework <i>Jakacki, Diane Katherine; Brown, Susan; Cummings, James; Ilovan, Mihaela; Milio, Rachel</i>	48
Multilingual taxonomy initiative - TaDiRAH as community of practice <i>Borek, Luise; Hastik, Canan; Dombrowski, Quinn; Broeder, Daan; Rockenberger, Annika; Nagasaki, Kiyonori; Mochizuki, Ryo; Katakura, Shumpei; Cupar, Drahomira; Ohmukai, Ikki</i>	50
OCR4all - Open-Source OCR and HTR Across the Centuries <i>Langhanki, Florian; Wehner, Maximilian; Roeder, Torsten; Reul, Christian</i>	53
Put Them In to Get Them Out: the ParlaMint Corpora for Digital Humanities and Social Sciences Research <i>Fišer, Darja; Kryvenko, Anna; Osenova, Petya; Pahor de Maitti, Kristina</i>	56

Semantic Web and Linked Open Data in Historical Sciences <i>Kröger, Bärbel; Störiko, Johanna Sophia; Wettlaufer, Jörg</i>	57
SIG-DLS Seven Years on <i>Rebora, Simone; Byszuk, Joanna; Frontini, Francesca; Herrmann, J. Berenike; Mpouli, Suzanne; Ruiz Fabo, Pablo</i>	59
SPARQL for (Digital) Humanists – Querying Wikidata and the MiMoTextBase <i>Röttgermann, Julia; Duan, Tinghui; Hinzmann, Maria; Klee, Anne; Konstanciak, Johanna; Schöch, Christof; Steffes, Moritz</i>	60
<i>The Programming Historian: Developing a Digital Humanities Tutorial</i> <i>Kleinman, Scott; Wermer-Colan, Alex; Vieira Paulino, Joana; Siddiqui, Nabeel; LeBlanc, Zoe</i>	63
Tutorial - Collaborative approaches to discourse: Music scholarship using performance recordings and Linked Data annotations <i>Lewis, David; Page, Kevin; VanderHart, Chanda; Weigl, David M.</i>	65
TwinTalks 4: Understanding and Facilitating Remote Collaboration in DH <i>Fišer, Darja; Krauwer, Steven; Chambers, Sally; Bernadou, Agiatis; van der Lek-Ciudin, Iulianna</i>	67
Who are the Users in Multilingual DH Research?: A Community Exploration <i>Horvath, Aliz; Wagner, Cosima; Wrisley, David</i>	69
Workshop CATMA featuring GitMA and Vis-A-Vis <i>Schumacher, Mareike Katharina; Gerstorfer, Dominik; Gius, Evelyn; Meister, Malte; Münz-Manor, Ophir</i>	71
Workshop HTR-United: metadata, quality control and sharing process for HTR training data <i>Clérice, Thibault; Chagué, Alix</i>	73

Short Presentations

A Catalogue of the Hebrew Sounds <i>Silber-Varod, Vered; Cohen, Evyatar; Strull, Inbar; Cohen, Evan Gary</i>	77
Accented DH: Assessing Fairness of Multilingual Speech Recognition Systems <i>Yokoyama, Setsuko; Rajan, Sai Sathiesh; Chattopadhyay, Sudipta</i>	78
Acoustical Cultural Heritages at the Centre of Cultural Exchanges. Origins and Distribution Patterns of Organ Building in South-East Europe <i>Ukolov, Dominik</i>	79
AI-supported indexing of handwritten dialect lexis: The pilot study "DWA Austria" as a case study. <i>Kunzmann, Markus</i>	80
A Model of Heaven: Tracing Images of Holiness in a Collection of 63.000 Lantern Slides (1880-1940) <i>Paklons, Eleonora; Smits, Thomas</i>	81
Analysis of Cyber Threats Affecting the Survivability of Online Digital Projects <i>Meneses, Luis; Martin, Jonathan</i>	82
An Undue Burden: Race, Gender, and Mobility in Digital Humanities Conferences <i>Siddiqui, Nabeel</i>	83
A Proposal for the Demarcation of Digital Humanities <i>Gonzalez-Perez, Cesar; Rojas Castro, Antonio; Fernández Travieso, Carlota; Merino Recalde, David; Díez-Platas, Fátima; Alvite-Diez, María-Luisa; Díez-Platas, M^a Luisa; Luengo, Pedro; Pereira-Fariña, Martín</i>	84
Augmenting the Metadata of Audiovisual Archives with NLP Techniques: Challenges and Solutions <i>Alliata, Giacomo; Yang, Yuchen; Kenderdine, Sarah</i>	86
Automatic Word Segmentation for Egyptian Hieroglyphic Texts <i>Jauhainen, Heidi; Jauhainen, Tommi</i>	87
Bringing the <i>New Variorum Shakespeare</i> Online <i>Mandell, Laura; Torabi, Katayoun; Tarpley, Bryan</i>	88
Building a digital edition from archived social media content <i>Kurzmeier, Michael; O'Sullivan, James; Pidd, Mike; Murphy, Orla; Wessels, Bridgette; Whittle, Sophie</i>	89
Casting the net far and wide: Aggregating and harmonizing epistolary metadata in collaboration with cultural heritage institutions <i>Drobac, Senka; Enqvist, Johanna; Leskinen, Petri; Wahjoe, Muhammad Faiz; Rantala, Heikki; Koho, Mikko; Pikkanen, Ilona; Jauhainen, Iida; Tuominen, Jouni; Paloposki, Hanna-Leena; La Mela, Matti; Hyvönen, Eero</i>	90
Challenges, opportunities, and recommendations for the future of crowdsourcing in cultural heritage: a White Paper <i>Ridge, Mia; Ferriter, Meghan; Blickhan, Samantha</i>	92
Collaboration practices between people and tools: the case of “ <i>Snorra Edda. A collaborative bibliography</i> (SnECB)” <i>Cipolla, Maria Adele; Cappellotto, Anna; Rospocher, Marco</i>	93
Collaboration, Preservation and Sustainability in Digital Humanities: a question of time <i>Aubert, Olivier; Stratil, Jasper</i>	95

Collaboration with citizens and its revolutionary potential in the digital humanities <i>Heinisch, Barbara</i>	96
Collecting Pieces of Historical Knowledge from Documents: Introduction of HIMIKO (Historical Micro Knowledge and Ontology) <i>Ogawa, Jun; Ohmukai, Ikki; Nakamura, Satoru; Kitamoto, Asanobu</i>	97
Comparing Perceptions of Literary Quality <i>van Dalen-Oskam, Karina; Groes, Bas; Byrne, Aidan; Harvey, Peter; Leguina, Adrian; Mercer, Tom; Wilton, Demi-Mae</i>	99
<i>Constrained</i> . A Computational Study of the Influence of Formal Characteristics on the Transmission of the Middle Dutch <i>Martijn trilogy</i> by Jacob van Maerlant <i>Moors, Sofie</i>	100
Constructing the GOLEM: Graphs and Ontologies for Literary Evolution Models <i>Pianzola, Federico; Yang, Xiaoyan; Visser, Noa; van der Ree, Michiel; van Cranenburgh, Andreas</i>	101
Contact zones / Third spaces European Summer University in Digital Humanities “Culture & Technology” (ESU DH C&T) <i>Burr, Elisabeth; Fußbahn, Ulrike</i>	102
correspSearch v2.2 – Search historical correspondence <i>Dumont, Stefan; Grabsch, Sascha; Müller-Laackman, Jonas; Sander, Ruth</i>	104
Creating a collaborative research platform for Vedic Sanskrit texts <i>Fischer, Anna; Kiss, Borge; Casaretto, Antje; Kölligan, Daniel; Korobzow, Natalie; Neufeind, Claes; Reinöhl, Uta; Sahle, Patrick</i>	105
Creating digital collections of the ancient epigraphic heritage in Bulgaria through collaboration <i>Iliev, Dimitar; Sharankov, Nicolay</i>	107
Creating user profiles based on citizen scientists' engagement patterns <i>Van Galen, Coen; van Oort, Thunnis; Prats López, Montserrat; Wessel, Ganzevoort; Mourits, Rick</i>	108
CreoPhonPt: a collaborative database saving Portuguese creoles from digital obliteration <i>Sousa e Silva, Carlos Rogério; Pimentel Trigo, Luis Manuel</i>	109
Cross-Cultural Classics: Preliminary Findings from Goodreads Based in the U.S. and Douban Based in China <i>Hu, Yuerong; Underwood, Ted; Layne-Worthey, Glen; Downie, J. Stephen</i>	110
Deep mapping in digital literary studies – polish experience <i>Niciński, Konrad Krzysztof; Zalotyńska, Agnieszka Maria</i>	111
Developing a Pipeline for Automatic Linguistic Analysis of Historical Manuscripts and Early Printings: The Pre-Modern Slavic Case <i>Rabus, Achim; Arnold, Eckhart; Jouravel, Anna; Lendvai, Piroška; Meindl, Martin; Polomac, Vladimir; Renje, Elena</i>	112
Developing criteria and collaborative work on inclusion in cultural heritage digitization projects <i>Priani Saiso, Ernesto; Galina Russel, Isabel</i>	113
Digital Maternal Cultures: The Politics of Collaboration in/and Indian Mommy Blogs <i>Roy, Dibyadyuti; Das, Madhurima</i>	115
Digital Prosopography and Global Irish Networks <i>O'Connor, Thomas; Angelis, Stavros; Fitzpatrick, Richard</i>	115
Digitizing the Messkataloge: Revealing the History of German Publishers, Authors and Translators <i>Tharsen, Jeffrey; Kretz, David</i>	116
Disentangling scientific fields using temporal clustering <i>Vogl, Malte; Lalli, Roberto</i>	118
Documenting Workflows for HTR to TEI Conversions for Cultural Institutions: The Evolving Hands Project <i>Cummings, James; Healey, Alexandra; Jakacki, Diane; Flex, Valentina; Jeffrey, Evie; Pirmann, Carrie; Johnson, Ian</i>	119
Eulalie: a documentary system for the collaborative preservation of electroacoustic music based on the Doremus ontology <i>Bardiot, Clarisse; Jacquemin, Bernard; Michaan, Alexandre; Westeel, Jeanne; Southammavong, Oudom; Koskowitz, Daniel</i>	120
Exploring genderlect markers in a corpus of Nineteenth century Spanish novels <i>Bermúdez Sabel, Helena</i>	121
Exploring legacies of race and slavery in our historical information environment: text analysis of the <i>Encyclopaedia Britannica</i> <i>Charlton, Ash</i>	123
Exploring topics surrounding migration in Austrian historical newspapers. Topic modelling of historical newspapers <i>Krušić, Lucija</i>	124
Finding Haiku – Enhancing Findability and Accessibility of Poetry Resources in Multi-genre Collections across Different Languages <i>Mrugalski, Michał; Charvat, Vera Maria; Börner, Ingo; Durco, Matej; Laszkovits, Sabine; Resch, Stefan</i>	125

From MemoRekall to MemoRekall-IIIF: developing a video annotation web application in the context of citizen science co-creation practices <i>Bardiot, Clarisse; Rouquet, David; Michaan, Alexandre; Blin, Irénée; Menassel, Mei; Hildebrand, Sébastien; Hart, Jacob; Ferrando, Stefania; Graffione, Cosetta; Marranca, Daniele</i>	127
From unstructured texts to RDF-star-based open research data queryable by references <i>Alassi, Sepideh</i>	128
Genre Identification and Network Analysis on Modern Chinese Prose Poetry <i>Ning, Cheng; Wei, Zhao</i>	130
Giorgio Bassani's notes between tradition and innovation <i>Siciliano, Angela; Del Grosso, Angelo Mario</i>	132
GIS application to determine settlement patterns in the Late Roman and Late Antique period <i>Tobalina-Pulido, Leticia</i>	134
Growing and Pruning the Republic of Letters: An Agent-Based Model to Build Letter Correspondence Networks <i>Buarque, Bernardo; Vogl, Malte</i>	135
Hand in Hand: Strauss' <i>Kaiser Walzer</i> as a case study of interdisciplinary collaboration in digital musicology <i>VanderHart, Chanda; Nurmikko-Fuller, Terhi; Weigl, David M.</i>	137
How to Be Non-Assertive in the 'Assertive Edition': Encoding Doubt in the <i>Auden Musulin Papers</i> <i>Frühwirth, Timo; Carloni, Massimiliano; Grigoriou, Dimitra; Mayer, Sandra; Stoxreiter, Daniel</i>	139
Human, Technology, and Culture Interaction? Mapping the Landscape of Technological 'Sister' Disciplines <i>Edmond, Jennifer; Treusch, Pat</i>	140
imgs.ai. A Deep Visual Search Engine for Digital Art History <i>Offert, Fabian; Bell, Peter</i>	141
"I'm here to fight for ground truth": HTR-United, a solution towards a common for HTR training data <i>Chagué, Alix; Clérice, Thibault</i>	142
Implementation of data-driven historical informatics research on Kao (Stylized Signature) <i>Nakamura, Satoru; Liu, Guanwei; Miyazaki, Hajime; Inoue, Satoshi; Ohyama, Wataru; Yamada, Taizo</i>	144
Investigating Constructivist Paradigms in Digital Humanities Scholarship <i>Kleymann, Rabea</i>	146
Investigating Decentralized Alternatives to Collaborative Long-term Research Data Preservation Infrastructure <i>Belouin, Pascal; Pham, Kim; Hennicke, Steffen</i>	147
Jacob Bernoulli's <i>Reisbüchlein</i> an RDF-star-based Edition <i>Ammann, Nora Olivia; Alassi, Sepideh; Rosenthaler, Lukas</i>	148
Let Everything be of Use?: Data Issues in Exploring the Publications and Networks of the Members of the Fruitbearing Society in the VD17 <i>Azizifard, Narges; Janicki, Maciej; Lindquist, Thea; Mäkelä, Eetu; Radio, Erik</i>	150
Magnetic Margins. A Census and Reader Annotations Database <i>Sander, Christoph; el-Hajj, Hassan; Adamou, Alessandro</i>	151
Making Digital Humanities teaching responsive to specificity of local context <i>Bhattacharyya, Sayan</i>	153
Mapping spatial named entities from noisy OCR output: Epimetheus from OCR to map. <i>Koudoro-Parfait, Caroline; Alrahabi, Motasem; Dupont, Yoann; Lejeune, Gaël; Roe, Glenn</i>	154
Maps and parish sketches of Karol Perthées - data model and processing <i>Borek, Arkadiusz</i>	156
Maze of Garfinkel: Making sense of formulations in ethnomethodology <i>Türkoglu, Enes; Mertgens, Andreas</i>	157
Migration Novel as a Conversional Genre <i>Aledavood, Parham; E. Sinatra, Michael; Forest, Dominic</i>	158
Misrepresentations of online engagement: re-examining online audiences in the UK museum sector <i>Charlesworth, Ellen; Beresford, Andrew M.; Warwick, Claire; Impett, Leonardo</i>	159
Modeling Eco-Poetics and Eco-Politics in 20th Century Anglophone Climate Fiction: Toxic Water <i>Miller, Dez Mary; Wermer-Colan, Henry Alexander; Stefan, SaraGrace; Kane, Megan</i>	160
Nestroy Corpus Analysis (<i>NestroyCA</i>): NLP for 19 th century Austrian Drama <i>Laszakovits, Sabine; Katsikadeli, Christina</i>	161
On Burgundian (di)vine orators and other impostors: Stylometry of Late Medieval Rhetoricians <i>Camps, Jean-Baptiste; Salvati, Benedetta</i>	162
On the Relation of Sound and Suspense in Literary Fiction <i>Guhr, Svenja Simone; Algee-Hewitt, Mark Andrew</i>	166

Planning for Uncertainty: Collaborating to Build Trust in the Midst of Uncertainty in Digital Humanities Projects	
<i>Champagne, Ashley</i>	168
Polyphemus, a lexical database of the Ancient Greek papyri, and the Madrid Wordlist of Ancient Greek	
<i>Riaño Rupilanchas, Daniel</i>	168
Pose Annotation Project for Artworks: A participatory annotation platform for automated body pose estimation in art.	
<i>Bernasconi, Valentine; Negueruela del Castillo, Dario</i>	169
Probabilistic Modeling of Chronological Dates to Serve Machines and Scholars	
<i>Habring, Andreas; Nicolaou, Angelos; Luger, Daniel; Atzenhofer-Baumgartner, Florian; Lamming, Florian; Decker, Franziska; Aoun, Sandy; Kovács, Tamás; Vogeler, Georg; Holler, Martin</i>	171
Providing Digital Answers to Disciplinary Questions with Graph Literary Exploration Machine	
<i>Maryl, Maciej; Karlińska, Agnieszka; Walentynowicz, Wiktor; Walkowiak, Tomasz</i>	173
Publishing Parallels: Author-Publisher Collaboration in Digital Projects vs Print Monographs	
<i>Mulliken, Jasmine; Coleman, Catherine Nicole</i>	174
Putting (Linguistic) Research Data on a Map – The DiÖ <i>Sprachatlas</i> Tool	
<i>Pluschkovits, Markus; Bal, Jakob</i>	176
Reading Machines: promoting reading with computational text analysis	
<i>Ciotti, Fabio; Baldi, Alberto</i>	177
Re-navigating the Vernacular Language Movement and Chinese Translation Literature, 1898-1938: An Examination of Prefaces Using Topic Modeling	
<i>Chen, Sixing; Du, Keli; Li, Jin</i>	178
Replicating a Data-Driven Corpus Analysis: The Example of Academic Language	
<i>Andresen, Melanie; Pichler, Axel</i>	180
Results of Emotion Annotation in German Drama from 1650-1815	
<i>Schmidt, Thomas; Dennerlein, Katrin; Wolff, Christian</i>	181
Revolution or Evolution? AI-Driven Image Classification of Historical Prints	
<i>Vignoli, Michela; Gruber, Doris; Simon, Rainer</i>	184
Revolution through collaboration? An attempt to familiarize „old guards“ with DH	
<i>Nunn, Christopher Alexander; van Oorschot, Frederike; Fucker, Selina</i>	185
Rhythmic, Melodic and Vertical N-Gram Features as a Means of Studying Symbolic Music Computationally	
<i>McKay, Cory; Cumming, Julie; Fujinaga, Ichiro</i>	187
ÚRSCEÁL: Building and Analysing a Corpus of the early Irish-language Novel.	
<i>Tonra, Justin</i>	188
Russian-Ukrainian War Art: Data Collection and Analysis	
<i>Gagarina, Dinara</i>	189
Shanghai Memory as a case study of ideological impact on storytelling: the interplay between memory, language, and stories	
<i>Fu, Yaming; Mahony, Simon</i>	190
Short texts with fewer authors. Revisiting the boundaries of stylometry	
<i>Rebora, Simone</i>	191
Similarity-Based Clustering of Pre-Modern Arabic Names	
<i>Yousef, Tariq; Kinitz, Daniel</i>	194
Social Justice in the Digital Humanities Community of Practice	
<i>Schreibman, Susan; Papadopoulos, Costas; Ping Huang, Marianne; Scholger, Walter; Kuzman Šlogar, Koraljka</i>	195
Standards-based Digital Platform for Annotating Translations Seeks Collaborators	
<i>Melby, Alan K.; Browne, Jeremy; Marshall, Catherine</i>	196
Student Scientometrics – What do German Students of the Humanities Cite in their Term Papers?	
<i>Heming, Tim; Gutiérrez De la Torre, Silvia E.; Burghardt, Manuel</i>	197
Studying Parliamentary Economization using Topic Burstiness and Entropy	
<i>Ros, Ruben</i>	199
Supervised vs. unsupervised deep learning for medieval Hebrew manuscripts	
<i>Vasyutinsky Shapira, Daria; Rabaev, Irina; Alaasam, Reem; El-Sana, Jihad</i>	200
Tell Me the Truth. Validating the Semantic Alignment between the Annotation User Interface and the Knowledge Base	
<i>Bonora, Paolo; Dello Buono, Martina; Giovannetti, Francesca; Tomasi, Francesca</i>	202
The creation of ‘Uvira’s Pot’, a virtual reality puzzle to promote engagement with archaeological research.	
<i>Hardy, Kristine</i>	204

The digital edition as a nexus of documents and data for historical research: the example of the Imperial Diet records of 1576	
<i>Bleier, Roman; Ortlieb, Eva; Zeilinger, Florian</i>	205
There is no “I” in “Infrastructure”: Creating a shared data-centric DH Infrastructure for Cultural Heritage Research in Saxony/Germany	
<i>Goldhahn, Dirk; Mühleder, Peter; Naether, Franziska</i>	206
They're veGAN but they almost taste the same: generating simili-manuscripts with artificial intelligence	
<i>Camps, Jean-Baptiste; Vidal-Gorène, Chahan</i>	207
Three rings, one story? Reconstructing the historical connectivity of religious encounters within the OTRA project (Ontology for the Transmission and Re-Use of Argumentative Patterns)	
<i>Langeloh, Jacob</i>	210
Towards a computationally aware approach to humanistic data interfaces	
<i>Sollazzo, Anna</i>	211
Towards a Conflict Heuristic. Detecting Conflict in Literary Texts By Adapting Word Embedding Based Sentiment Analysis	
<i>Häußler, Julian; Gius, Evelyn</i>	213
Towards a <i>distant viewing</i> of depicted materials in medieval paintings	
<i>Nicka, Isabella; Uhl, Andreas; Landkammer, Miriam; Linortner, Michael; Schuiki, Johannes</i>	214
Towards a Dynamic Knowledge Graph of a Non-Western Book Tradition	
<i>Kinitz, Daniel; Efer, Thomas</i>	216
Towards Metadata-enriched Literary Corpora in Line with FAIR Principles: 19/20MetaPNC	
<i>Rosiński, Cezary; Karlińska, Agnieszka; Kubis, Marek; Hubar, Patryk; Wieczorek, Jan</i>	217
Tracing the invisible translator: stylistic differences in the Dutch translations of the oeuvre of Swedish author Henning Mankell	
<i>Wijers, Martje</i>	218
Transhistorical Resonance: Medieval Chinese Scholarship as Data	
<i>Budak, Nicholas Andrew; Rominger, Gian Duri</i>	219
Turning the Carniolan regional assembly proceedings into an enriched historical corpus	
<i>Marolt, Matija; Gašparič, Jure; Mundjar, Aleksander; Kavčič, Alenka; Fišer, Darja; Pančur, Andrej</i>	221
Using Digital Tools to Map the Movement of Capital, People and Culture from Slave-owning Britain to Western Australia	
<i>Arthur, Paul; Smith, Isabel; Lydon, Jane; Martens, Jeremy; Laidlaw, Zoë</i>	222
Using Github Issues to facilitate the project communication between developers and humanists. Case study	
<i>Szulińska, Agnieszka</i>	224
Using Multimodal Machine Learning to Distant View the Illustrated World of the <i>Illustrated London News</i> , 1842-1900	
<i>Smits, Thomas; Lee, Ben; Fyfe, Paul</i>	225
Viewing Between the Lines: Representation of Age, Race, Class and Gender in the Illustrations of Dutch-Language Children's Literature (1800-1940)	
<i>Van der Eecken, Paavo</i>	227
Visiting Vienna – digital approaches to the (semi-)automatic analysis and mapping of the arrival lists found in the "Wien[n]erisches Diarium"	
<i>Rastinger, Nina C.</i>	228
Visualization as an epistemic tool for multimodal sources in the history of education	
<i>Freyberg, Linda</i>	229
Visualizing Cities: H.P. Lovecraft's Providence, Rhode Island	
<i>Szabo, Victoria; Monteleone, Cosimo</i>	231
What's the Use? Exploring Non-academic Applications of (Computational) Literary Studies	
<i>Edmond, Jennifer; Yakupova, Vera</i>	232
"With the Same name and adrvocation of S.Juan there is another one, in the sameprovince"- towards a digital edition of the historical-geographical dictionary of the Indies by Antonio de Alcedo	
<i>Stangl, Werner; Brando, Carmen; Zúñiga, Jean-Paul; Haedo, Anahi</i>	233
Words Shape Characters: A Case Study of Correspondence Analysis on Characters' Words in <i>The Tale of Genji</i>	
<i>Takeuchi, Ayano; Ogiso, Toshinobu</i>	234
Zero-shot keyword spotting, using CLIP for modern manuscripts	
<i>Verreyen, Loren</i>	236

Long Presentations

Access & Discovery of Documentary Images (ADDI): A Platform for the Exploration and Critique of Computer Vision Algorithms <i>Arnold, Taylor; Tilton, Lauren</i>	239
A Clash of Colorful Worlds. Distant Viewing Color in Western Visual Representations of the Orient and Occident, 1890-1920 <i>Wevers, Melvin; Smits, Thomas</i>	240
A Gateway to Science: Fostering Access, Exchange, and Use of Social Science and Humanities Research Through a Digital Discovery Platform <i>Blotière, Emilie; Disch, Leonie; Breidfuss, Gert; Cupar, Drahomira; Stojanovski, Jadranka</i>	243
Age, Sex, and Diseases of Dead People - Integrating Anthropological Analysing Methods into DH Tools <i>Richards, Nina; Eichert, Stefan; Watzinger, Alexander; Koschicek-Krombholz, Bernhard; Olschnögger, Andreas; Hoffmann, Christoph; Großfurther, Moritz</i>	245
A Knowledge Graph for Humanities Research <i>Pertsas, Vayianos; Leontaridis, Panagiotis; Kasapaki, Marialena; Constantopoulos, Panos</i>	246
A Philosophical View of the Digital History of Concepts: Four Theses And a Postscript <i>Heßbrüggen-Walter, Stefan</i>	247
Are Ret Marut and B. Traven the same person? Fine tuning the impostors method <i>Rebora, Simone; Salgaro, Massimo; Sopcak, Paul</i>	248
Art History and Artificial Intelligence: Opportunities and Challenges of Large-Scale Visual Models in the Digital Humanities <i>Offert, Fabian; Impett, Leonardo</i>	250
Artificial Intelligence for the analysis of Cultural Heritage point clouds <i>Paolanti, Marina; Matrone, Francesca; Uricchio, Tiberio; Giovanola, Benedetta; Frontoni, Emanuele; Lingua, Andrea Maria; Pierdicca, Roberto</i>	252
A speculative design for future handwritten text recognition: HTR use, and its impact on historical research and the digital record. <i>Nockels, Joe; Terras, Melissa; Gooding, Paul</i>	254
A Statistical Exploration of the Hypothesized Partition of the Books of Genesis and Exodus into Priestly and non-Priestly Components <i>Yoffe, Gideon; Buehler, Axel; Roemer, Thomas; Dershowitz, Nachum; Piasetzky, Eli; Finkelstein, Israel; Sober, Barak</i>	256
Becoming the digital humanities as discourse(s) of subjectivation <i>Petz, Cindarella</i>	258
Building Digital Capacities through Collaboration. The case of Proyecto Humboldt Digital (Havana/Berlin) <i>Kraft, Tobias; Rojas Castro, Antonio; Terrón, Grisel; Solernou, Alaina; Guerra, Eritk; Kirsten, Linda</i>	260
Can Machine Translation of Literary Texts Fool Stylometry? <i>Rybicki, Jan</i>	261
Co-encoding embodied knowledge in Southern Chinese martial arts: a collaboration between computists, experts, and digital models <i>Hou, Yumeng</i>	264
<i>Colette, Curnonsky, and the Willy workshop.</i> Assessing relative contributions and influences beyond “collaborative authorship” <i>Cafiero, Florian; Puren, Marie</i>	266
Collaboration Across the Archival and Computational Sciences to Address Legacies of Gender Bias in Descriptive Metadata <i>Havens, Lucy; Hosker, Rachel; Alex, Beatrice; Bach, Benjamin; Terras, Melissa</i>	267
Collaboration as Necessity: Institutional Support for Digital Humanities Research <i>Blumtritt, Jonathan; Gengnagel, Tessa; Horstmann, Jan; Neufeind, Claes</i>	270
Communication Landscapes of the 19th Century: The Speed, Geographical Coverage and Content of News in the <i>Rigasche Zeitung</i> <i>Kruusmaa, Krister</i>	272
Community-centric factors in sustaining digital scholarship <i>Fenlon, Katrina; Reza, Alia; Grimmer, Jessica; Wagner, Travis</i>	273
Computing Angel Names in Jewish Magic <i>Saar, Ortal-Paz; van Eijnatten, Joris</i>	275
Connecting Art and Science for Humanities Research: Mapping Color in History <i>Kim, Jinah; Crawford, Cole; Singhal, Rashmi; Steward, Jeff</i>	277
contextualize - connect - collaborate: The Architecture Research Stage as an Experimental Pilot Project <i>Dürfeld, Michael; List, Ferdinand; Stein, Christian; Rahman, Zead; Dias, Renata</i>	278

Cultural Motifs on #bigdata - A Semi-Automated Topic Modeling from a Socio-Cultural Constructionist Perspective	
<i>Knorr, Charlotte; Niekler, Andreas; Behret, Marius; Pentzold, Christian</i>	281
Data narratives with Linked Open Data, the case of mythLOD storytelling	
<i>Pasqual, Valentina; Tomasi, Francesca</i>	283
Data Problems in the Humanities, or "When everybody is special, no one is"?	
<i>Woods, Nathan D.; Bordalejo, Barbara; O'Donnell, Daniel Paul</i>	285
Data Remediation as Collaborative Process	
<i>Martin, Kim; Brown, Susan</i>	287
Digital Edition of Complete Tolstoy's Heritage: OCR Crowd Sourcing Initiative, Literary Scholarship and User Scenarios	
<i>Bonch-Osmolovskaya, Anastasia; Orekhov, Boris; Tolstaya, Fekla</i>	288
Digitization of the Inscriptions on the Monuments of Armenian Cultural Heritage in Nagorno-Karabakh Region	
<i>Tamrazyan, Hamest</i>	289
Digitizing Suzette: Creating a Framework for the Collaborative Analysis of an Historical French Textbook	
<i>Westbrook, John; Jakacki, Diane; Heintzelman, Rebecca; Harnood, Juliya</i>	291
Distortion: Authority, Authenticity, and Agency in Zora Neale Hurston's Black Folk Recordings	
<i>Clement, Tanya</i>	292
Dockerizing DraCor – A Container-based Approach to Reproducibility in Computational Literary Studies	
<i>Boerner, Ingo; Trilcke, Peer; Milling, Carsten; Fischer, Frank; Sluyter-Gäthje, Henny</i>	293
D or H – What leads in DH? Envisaging the Digital Humanities Space in India	
<i>Ghosh, Sharanya; Dahiya, Vasundhara; Dahiya, Lavanya; Chadha, Aanya</i>	295
Enlightenment Influencers: Networks of Text Reuse in 18th-century France	
<i>Roe, Glenn; Fedchenko, Valentina; Nicolosi, Dario</i>	296
Exploring the Evolution of Curatorial Diversity: a Methodological Framework with a Case Study of Book Reviews	
<i>Calderon Reyes, Emilio</i>	299
Factors of Literary History: The Case of German-language Poetry (1850–1920)	
<i>Konle, Leonard; Kröncke, Merten; Jannidis, Fotis; Winko, Simone</i>	301
Feature Engineering for US State Legislative Hearings: Stance, Affiliation, Engagement and Absentees	
<i>Grace, Joshua; Khosmood, Foaad</i>	303
Finding Fascists, Efficiently! Comparing methods for mapping attitudes in Dutch and Belgian historical newspaper corpora (1920-1940)	
<i>van den Heede, Pieter; van Lange, Milan; Futselaar, Ralf</i>	305
Fostering collaboration for open access publishing models: a study of the Polish ecosystem in the area of open access monographs in the humanities	
<i>Wnuk, Magdalena; Błaszczczyńska, Marta; Świetlik, Marta</i>	307
Fragmentation and Disruption: Ranking Cut-Points in Epistolary Networks at the Court of Henry VIII	
<i>Burge, Caitlin Rose</i>	308
From Atoms to Eternity: Visualizing Space and Scale in Emily Dickinson	
<i>Lang, Anouk</i>	309
From Automated Bootstrapping to Collaborative Editing: A Framework for 4D City Reconstruction	
<i>Vaienti, Beatrice; Guhennec, Paul; Dupertuis, Didier; Petitpierre, Rémi</i>	310
From Tapestry to Data Visualisation: Networks of Collaboration in Project Cornelia	
<i>Lamqaddam, Houda; Beerens, Rudy Jos; Brosens, Koenraad; Cardoso, Bruno; de Prekel, Inez; Truyen, Frederik; Van der Stighelen, Katlijne; Verbert, Katrien; Fantoli, Margherita</i>	313
From Theoretical Texts to Concept Maps. An Annotation Approach for a Distant Reading of Argumentative Text Structures.	
<i>Tulai, Radu; Viehhauser, Gabriel; Angermeier, Jan; Taban, Gökce</i>	314
From There to Posterity: Modelling Diverse Itineraries of Scientific Instruments	
<i>Middle, Sarah; Butterworth, Alex; Higgitt, Rebekah</i>	318
Genetic networks: data model and visualisations	
<i>Spadini, Elena; Christen, Alessio; Pallacci, Valentina; Elli, Tommaso; Benedetti, Andrea; Maggetti, Daniel; Mauri, Michele; Pétermann, Stéphanie</i>	319
Graph schema validation at last? Revisiting the Stemmarest data model with Neo4J and SHACL	
<i>Andrews, Tara Lee</i>	321
Handwritten text recognition applied to the manuscript production of the Carthusian Monastery of Herne in the Fourteenth Century	
<i>Haverals, Wouter; Kestemont, Mike</i>	322

How Corpus Analysis Helps Operationalize Research Questions and Entices Literary Scholars to Learn Programming	
<i>Cinková, Silvie; Cvrček, Václav; Janssen, Maarten; Křen, Michal</i>	323
Humanistic NLP: Bridging the Gap Between Digital Humanities and Natural Language Processing	
<i>Tasovac, Toma; Ermolaev, Natalia; Janco, Andrew; Lassner, David; Budak, Nick</i>	325
Image Classification of Paris Bible Data	
<i>Abo Bakir Shuan, Yasmin Hawar; Meinecke, Christofer; Jänicke, Stefan</i>	326
Implicit Gender Inequality in Children's Picture Books: Evidence from a Text Mining Analysis of 200 Bestselling Chinese and British Titles	
<i>Li, Yi; Terras, Melissa; Li, Yongning</i>	328
Improving publication processes of the Association for Digital Humanities in the German Speaking Areas (DHd) - The DHd Data Steward and the community-driven Task Force "DHd Abstracts"	
<i>Debbeler, Anke; Helling, Patrick; Borges, Rebekka</i>	331
Innovators of the Past: Modelling Novelty and Resonance in Dutch Historical Language Records	
<i>Lassche, Alie; Ros, Ruben</i>	333
Investigating multisemiotic persuasive practices by integrating computational methods and complementary theoretical frameworks. A Data-driven Approach to Digital Tourism Discourse Based on Systemic Functional Linguistics and Empirical Multimodality	
<i>Mattei, Elena</i>	336
"It's as simple as asking for it". How do archaeologists collaborate – and how can open data improve it (or not)	
<i>Battle Baró, Sabina</i>	337
Linking (In)Completeness: A Collaborative Approach to Representing People in Art Provenance Data	
<i>Rother, Lynn; Mariani, Fabio; Koss, Max</i>	338
Link Visions Together: Visualizing Geographies of Late Qing and Republican China	
<i>Che, Qun; Lin, Nungyao; Chen, Shih-Pei; Yeh, Calvin</i>	340
Localizing Community Resilience within the Digital Humanities: Examples from the Penghu Archipelago	
<i>Streiter, Oliver; Zhan, Ya-qing; Goudin, Yoann</i>	341
Machine Learning and Digital Classical Chinese Texts: Collaboration between the UC Computing Platform and Peking University's Big-Data databases.	
<i>Hu, Minghui; Li, Xiao; Weekley, Jeffrey</i>	346
Making Hobbes's Bible in the English Political Works Machine-Readable: A TXM-Based Workflow	
<i>Rebasti, Francesca; Heiden, Serge</i>	346
Manu McFrench, from zero to hero: impact of using a generic handwriting model for smaller datasets	
<i>Chagué, Alix; Clérice, Thibault; Norindr, Jade; Humeau, Maxime; Davoury, Baudouin; Van Kote, Elsa; Mazoue, Anaïs; Faure, Margaux; Doat, Soline</i>	349
Mapping Antiquity in Collaboration: The Digital Periegesis Project	
<i>Foka, Anna; Barker, Elton; Konstantinidou, Kyriaki; Kiesling, Brady</i>	351
Mapping German Fiction in Translation Visualizing Translationalism in the German National Library Catalogue	
<i>Teichmann, Lisa</i>	353
Mapping Memes in the Napoleonic Cadastre: Expanding Frontiers in Memetics	
<i>Petitpierre, Rémi</i>	354
Marco Polo's Travels Revisited: From Motion Event Detection to Optimal Path Computation in 3D Maps	
<i>Niekler, Andreas; Wolska, Magdalena; Thiel, Marvin; Wiegmann, Matti; Stein, Benno; Burghardt, Manuel</i>	357
Maximising the Power of Semantic Textual Data: CASTEMO Data Collection and the InkVisitor Application	
<i>Zbiral, David; Shaw, Robert L. J.; Hampejs, Tomáš; Mertel, Adam</i>	359
Measuring the Uneven Digitization of Historical Literature	
<i>Evalyn, Lawrence Isaac</i>	361
Modeling the evolving social dynamics of political figures with chronological historical records	
<i>Chen, You-Jun; Hsieh, Hsin-Yi; Lin, Yu-Tung; Tsai, Richard Tzong-Han</i>	362
"Money Can't Buy Love?" Creating a Historical Sentiment Index for the Berlin Stock Exchange, 1872–1930	
<i>Borst, Janos; Wehrheim, Lino; Burghardt, Manuel</i>	365
More Social, Less Religious: Trends of Hardcover Fiction Titles on the New York Times Bestseller List 2000-2020	
<i>Bei der Wieden, Gesa; Bathurst, Taylor; Haider, Thomas Nikolaus</i>	367
Multimodal genre recognition of Chinese operas with hybrid fusion	
<i>Fan, Tao; Wang, Hao; Hodel, Tobias</i>	370
Networks at Scale. A Metadata-Based Approach to Detecting Links Between Fanfiction-Communities	
<i>Brottrager, Judith; Glawion, Anastasia; Herget, Katharina; Weitin, Thomas</i>	372

New pathways to research and library collaboration through remote technologies	
<i>Kamposiori, Christina</i>	375
Non-representational approaches to visualise complex information in the Cultural Heritage domain	
<i>Pasqual, Valentina; Pedretti, Carlo Teo; Schimmenti, Andrea; Tomasi, Francesca; Vitali, Fabio</i>	376
Observing semantic change in the representation of ethnic minorities through distant reading of museum catalogues	
<i>Kizhner, Inna; Netzer, Yael; Skorinkin, Daniil; Terras, Melissa; Lavee, Moshe</i>	378
Piloting A Machine Learning Approach to Identify English-Language Fiction in the HathiTrust Digital Library	
<i>Dubnicek, Ryan; Underwood, Ted</i>	381
Precision Archaeology: a computational approach to archeological risk assessment	
<i>Pierdicca, Roberto; Uricchio, Tiberio; Tadolti, Matteo; Paolanti, Marina; Frontoni, Emanuele; Perna, Roberto</i>	382
Pre-Modern Data: Applying Language Modeling and Named Entity Recognition on Criminal Records in the City of Bern	
<i>Hodel, Tobias; Prada Ziegler, Ismail; Schneider, Christa</i>	384
Presence and Absence of Women in Early Modern Handwritten News: Random Walks in the Medici Archive	
<i>Toth, Gabor Mihaly</i>	385
Proto-editions: Historians and the "Something between digital image and digital scholarly edition"	
<i>Vogeler, Georg</i>	387
Putting to test the Affective-Aesthetic Potential	
<i>Boot, Peter; Koolen, Marijn; Mussman, Ole; Schnober, Carsten; van Hage, Willem; van Zundert, Joris</i>	389
Read All About It: Digital Participation in Australian Literary History	
<i>Bode, Katherine; Cuthbertson, Galen; Osborne, Roger</i>	392
Representation of critical discourses in the humanities within Wikidata	
<i>Di Pasquale, Alessio; Pasqual, Valentina; Tomasi, Francesca; Vitali, Fabio</i>	393
Representing provenance and track changes of cultural heritage metadata in RDF: a survey of existing approaches	
<i>Massari, Arcangelo; Peroni, Silvio; Tomasi, Francesca; Heibi, Ivan</i>	395
Scholarly Digital Editions: APIs and Reuse Scenarios	
<i>Spadini, Elena; Losada Palenzuela, José Luis</i>	398
Software Citation in the Digital Humanities	
<i>Jetka, Daniel; Henny-Krahmer, Ulrike; Ferger, Anne; Alvares Freire, Fernanda</i>	400
Student-Focused Digital Projects in Short-Term Study Abroad Experiences	
<i>Applegate, Matt; Evans, Sarah; Schmidt, Katherine</i>	402
Systematic Gender Asymmetries in Aesthetic Judgments: An Observational Study of Book Reviewer Preferences	
<i>Lassen, Ida Marie S.; Bizzoni, Yuri; Thomsen, Mads R.; Nielbo, Kristoffer</i>	404
The Dots and the Line. How to Visualize the Argumentative Structure of an Essay	
<i>Parigini, Margherita; Mauri, Michele</i>	406
The 'Environmental Scan' at work: radical contextualisation of newspaper collections for new historical research	
<i>Beelen, Kaspar; Lawrence, Jon; McDonough, Katherine; Westerling, Kalle; Wilson, Daniel C.S.</i>	408
"The research is happening in the text fields" – Are Linked Open Data and Art History a good match?	
<i>Nanni, Giacomo; Freyberg, Linda; de Günther, Sabine; Dörk, Marian</i>	409
The Skin of Venice: Automatic Facade Extraction from Point Clouds.	
<i>Guhennec, Paul; di Lenardo, Isabella</i>	411
To accuse or not to accuse: a network analysis of incriminations in a medieval inquisition register	
<i>Riccardo, Katia; Zbiral, David</i>	413
"Together" : interdisciplinarity, collaboration and participation in digital cultural heritage research. The case of the Congruence Engine project	
<i>Sichani, Anna-Maria; Rees, Arran; Zardini, Stefania</i>	415
Topo-biographies of Women, "Austria," and Textual and Spatial Methods	
<i>Booth, Alison</i>	416
Tracing the Shift to "Objectivity" in German Encyclopedias of the Long Nineteenth Century	
<i>Hagen, Thora; Konle, Leonard; Ketzan, Erik; Jannidis, Fotis; Witt, Andreas</i>	418
Transformer-Based Named Entity Recognition for Ancient Greek	
<i>Yousef, Tariq; Palladino, Chiara; Jänicke, Stefan</i>	420
Uncovering Principles of Sustainability in Literature	
<i>Schumacher, Mareike Katharina; Gius, Evelyn</i>	423

Using ECCO-BERT and the Historical Thesaurus of English to Explore Concepts and Agency in Historical Writing Interpreting the Eighteenth-century Luxury Debate <i>Liimatta, Aatu; Mäkelä, Eetu; Ginter, Filip; Rastas, Iiro; Tihonen, Iiro; Zhang, Jinbin; Pivovarova, Lidia; Tolonen, Mikko; K, Milja; Babbar, Rohit; Wang, Ruilin; Säily, Tanja; Ryan, Yann Ciarán</i>	424
Visualizing and Analyzing Voting Records from Historical Documents <i>Cantareira, Gabriel Dias; Cole, Nicholas; Abdul-Rahman, Alfie</i>	427
Word Clouds with Spatial Stable Word Positions across Multiple Text Witnesses <i>Dähne, Janis; Pöckelmann, Marcus; Ritter, Jörg</i>	429
Word2Vec-Based Literary Networks - Challenges and Opportunities <i>Marienberg-Millikowsky, Itay; Vilenchick, Dan</i>	431
Zoetrope – Interactive Feature Exploration in News Videos <i>Liebl, Bernhard; Burghardt, Manuel</i>	432

Panels

Beyond the Boundaries of Individual Universities: Allegiance to Digital Humanities Education in Korea <i>Lee, Jae-Yon; Kim, Yongsoo; Ryu, Su-Rin; Mun, Soo-Hyun; Kim, Hyoungun</i>	436
Collaborative Visualizations and Visualizing Collaboration <i>Sutherland, Serenity; Nelson, David Ragnar; Ohge, Christopher; Bernardi, Joanne; Haak, Candis</i>	438
Enhancing research and teaching capacity through collaboration: building a UK-Ireland Digital Humanities Association <i>Winters, Jane; Donnay, Michael; Edmond, Jennifer; Murphy, Orla; Tupman, Charlotte; Gooding, Paul; Schuster, Kristen; Ciula, Arianna; Tonra, Justin</i>	440
Exploring the borderlands. A revolutionary potential for DH <i>Borek, Luise; Lang, Sarah; Dombrowski, Quinn; Fiormonte, Domenico; Metilli, Daniele; Murray, Padmini Ray; Roy, Dibyadyuti; Terras, Melissa</i>	442
Fostering Collaboration to Enable Bibliodata-driven Research in the Humanities <i>Malínek, Vojtěch; Umerle, Tomasz; Tolonen, Mikko; Karlińska, Agnieszka; Romanello, Matteo; Colavizza, Giovanni; Peroni, Silvio; Siwecka, Dorota; Lubocki, Jakub; Rißler-Pipka, Nanette; Lindemann, David; Labropoulou, Penny; Klaes, Christiane</i>	445
Intersectional Feminist Revolutions in Digital Humanities – approaches, histories, and methods <i>Webb, Sharon; Chevalier, Cécile; Naji, Jeneen; Fubara-Manuel, Irene; Fox, Izzy; Hill, Laurence</i>	448
It Takes a Village: Building an Infrastructure for 3D Scholarly Editions <i>Papadopoulos, Costas; Schreibman, Susan; Gillikin Schoueri, Kelly; Cope, Jamie; Blundell, Jon; Ogawa, Jun; Nagasaki, Kiyonori</i>	451
Legal Issues in Digital Humanities: Analysis of Recent Advocacy and Continuing and Emerging Issues <i>Ketzan, Erik; Nayyer, Kim; Dombrowski, Quinn; Tilton, Lauren; de Smedt, Koenraad; Kamocki, Pawel; Trollip, Benito; Nagasaki, Kiyonori</i>	453
Looking back to build future shared collections: reports from the Sloane Lab <i>Humbel, Marco; Valeonti, Foteini; Metilli, Daniele; Sadek, Jawad; Terracciano, Alda; Pickering, Victoria; Hughes, Alicia; Vlachidis, Andreas; Pearlman, Nina; Flinn, Andrew; Carine, Mark; Sloan, Kim; Nyhan, Julianne</i>	455
On Making in the Digital Humanities: The scholarship of digital humanities development in honour of John Bradley <i>Ortolja-Baird, Alexandra; Rockwell, Geoffrey; Nyhan, Julianne; Bradley, John; Ciula, Ariana; Broun, Davit</i>	458
Readers, Tropes, and Translations: Directions for Digital Research into Youth Literature <i>Backman, Agnieszka; Byszuk, Joanna; Dombrowski, Quinn; Lang, Anouk; Murath, Antonia; Nomura, Nichole</i>	461
Reception History in Many Dimensions: New Research on Book Reviews <i>Lavin, Matthew; Walsh, Melanie; Antoniak, Maria; Hu, Yuerong; Underwood, Ted; Bishop, David; Senatorova, Liza; Shang, Wenyi</i>	463
Research Software Engineer Careers and Project Involvement in DH <i>Damerow, Julia; Vogl, Malte; Tharsen, Jeffrey; Casties, Robert; Koester, Rebecca Sutton; LeBlanc, Zoe; Siqueira, Diego; Crawford, Cole</i>	466
The Pelagios Network: Collaboration as a Community of Practice <i>Barker, Elton; Gheldof, Tom; Gordin, Shai; Lewis, Orly; Nury, Elisa; Vitale, Valeria; Simon, Rainer; McDonough, Katherine; Chen, Anne; Williams, Miranda; Almohamad, Adnan; Middle, Sarah; Hay, Duncan; Butterworth, Alex</i>	467
Transforming the Pietist Tradition: Disciplinary Innovation through Linked Digital Engagement <i>Faull, Katherine Mary; Prell, Martin; Tögel, Philipp; Lasch, Alexander; Garces, Juan</i>	471
What We Teach When We Teach DH: Notes from the Field <i>Jakacki, Diane Katherine; Croxall, Brian; O'Sullivan, James; Langmead, Alison; Vee, Annette; Menon, Nirmala; Roy, Dibyadyuti; Tsui, Lik Hang; Zhu, Benjun; Chen, Jing</i>	473

Posters

A Digital Humanities Climate Coalition Toolkit for Researchers and Institutions <i>Ohge, Christopher; Baker, James; Otty, Lisa; Walton, Jo Lindsay</i>	478
A Feminist Approach to Linked Open Data: Making the Women Film Pioneers Project FAIR <i>Junginger, Pauline</i>	478
African Californios: Uncovering the African past of Spanish and Mexican California using Data Science Methods <i>Jones, Cameron; Witulski, Evan; Khosmood, Foaad</i>	480
AI-Assisted Performance Analysis: Deep Learning for Live and Archival Theater <i>Rau, Michael J.; Broadwell, Peter; Wiles, Simon; Abraham, Vijoy</i>	481
Archives and Database: The Chronicle of Modern Translation Literature in Chinese (Periodicals, 1896-1949) <i>Li, Jin; Zhu, Cuiping; Li, Huan</i>	482
A Study on the Emotional Measurements of Literary Geography from a Digital Humanities Perspective <i>Chen, Jing; Wang, Jiajie; Zheng, Yuning</i>	484
Bee-ing Human <i>G S, Balu; Hogg, Bennett; Nityananda, Vivek; Smith, Olivia; Sousa Garcia, Tiago; Richards, Jennifer; Williamson, Magnus</i>	485
Buddhist Murals of Kucha on the Northern Silk Road. A Follow Up on Semi Automated Annotation Using RCNNs. <i>Radisch, Erik</i>	486
Change Agents out of place Organizational Ambidexterity and Embeddedness as Key Concepts for DH Units in Humanities Institutions <i>Cremer, Fabian; Wübbena, Thorsten</i>	488
Characters, names and reference <i>Johnsen, Lars; Kåsen, Andre</i>	489
Collaboration and Professionalization. The role of software and Research Software Engineers in the Digital Humanities. <i>Czmiel, Alexander; Henny-Krahmer, Ulrike; Jettka, Daniel</i>	490
Collaboration in Practice: Data Comics in Learning Management Systems <i>Königshofer, Elisabeth; Wünsche, Katharina</i>	491
Collaboration within a shared digital paradigm: opportunities and outcomes <i>De Bastiani, Chiara; Fabbris, Giulia</i>	492
Collecting Strike Data from Historical Newspapers (19th Century): A Digital Workflow <i>Aurich, Jens</i>	494
Computational Literary Studies Infrastructure (CLS INFRA): Initial Findings and Conclusions for the Field <i>Birkholz, Julie M.; Börner, Ingo; Byszuk, Joanna; Chambers, Sally; Charvat, Vera Maria; Cinková, Silvie; Dejaeghere, Tess; Dudar, Julia; Ďurčo, Matej; Eder, Maciej; Edmond, Jennifer; Fileva, Evgeniia; Fischer, Frank; Garnett, Vicky; Heiden, Serge; Křen, Michal; Kunda, Bartłomiej; Laszakovits, Sabine; Mrugalski, Michał; Papaki, Eliza; Raciti, Marco; Resch, Stefan; Ros, Salvador; Schöch, Christof; Šeļa, Artjoms; Tasovac, Toma; Tonra, Justin; Tóth-Czifra, Erzsébet; Trilcke, Peer; van Dalen-Oskam, Karina; van Rossum, Lisanne</i>	496
Connecting Places In the World Historical Gazetteer <i>Grossner, Karl; Mostern, Ruth; Michalewicz, Nathan; Straub, Alexandra</i>	498
Content providers, Researchers, Technology and the Crowd: Discovering the Best Possible Collaborative Strategies for Datafication and Publication of a Dutch Historical Newspaper Corpus <i>Depuydt, Katrien; van der Sijs, Nicoline; de Does, Jesse; de Jong, Ruud; de Bonth, Roland; Fannee, Mathieu; Romein, Annemieke; van Zundert, Joris</i>	499
Crowdsourcing in History. New participatory and inclusive methodological challenges for research in History in Spain (CrowdHistory) <i>Bocanegra Barbecho, Lidia; Ortega Santos, Antonio</i>	501
Cuban digital collections: an approach for collaboration and innovation. <i>Terrón Quintero, Grisel; Guerra Figueredo, Eritk; Solernou Ferrer, Alaina; Echarri Ramirez, Bryan</i>	503
Data & Community: Building a Virtual Lab at the National Library of Estonia <i>Tinitis, Peeter; Sinisalu, Urmas; Meior, Marianne</i>	504
Datafication and reuse of the descriptions of the incunabula collection at the British Library <i>Atanassova, Rossitza</i>	505
Data Modeling as a High-Wire Act. Balancing Requirements, Juggling Vocabularies, and not Falling (Short of Established Best Practice) <i>Oberreither, Bernhard</i>	506

Developing a New Research Data Infrastructure for Japanese Historical Materials <i>Shibutani, Ayako; Nakamura, Satoru; Hirasawa, Kanako; Imukai, Honami; Yamada, Toshiyuki; Adachi, Airu; Ohmukai, Ikki; Yamada, Taizo</i>	507
Digital contributions to a 300 years old methodology: Diplomatics & DH <i>Luger, Daniel; Nicolaou, Angelos; Decker, Franziska; Atzenhofer-Baumgartner, Florian; Lammingner, Florian; Vogeler, Georg; Aoun, Sandy; Kovács, Tamás</i>	508
Digital Edition of Philipp Gumpenhuber's Chronicle of the Viennese Theatrical Life Between 1758 and 1763 <i>Zechner, Ingeborg; Beier, Mirijam; Galka, Selina</i>	510
Digital Edition of Roman Inscriptions from Serbia: A Work in Progress <i>Nikolić, Dragana</i>	511
Digitization as an opportunity for collaboration: digitizing personal correspondence from World War II at the intersection of history, archival science, and the digital humanities <i>van Lange, Milan Mikolaj; van Nispen, Annelies; Keijzer, Carlijn</i>	512
Distributed Corpus Building in Literary Studies: The DraCor Example <i>Giovannini, Luca; Skorinkin, Daniil; Trilcke, Peer; Börner, Ingo; Fischer, Frank; Dudar, Julia; Milling, Carsten; Pořizka, Petr</i>	513
Enabling Participatory Data Perspectives for Image Archives through a Linked Art Workflow <i>Raemy, Julien Antoine; Gray, Tanya; Collinson, Alwyn; Page, Kevin R.</i>	515
Enriching Exhibition Scholarship <i>Llewellyn, Clare; Sanderson, Robert; Page, Kevin; Bhaugeerutty, Aruna; Shapland, Andrew; Shipp, Kayla; David, Kelly; Delmas-Glass, Emmanuelle; Bonnet, Tyler</i>	516
Exil:Trans - a blueprint for research data reuse <i>Kremmel, Stefanie; Steiner, Christian; Pollin, Christopher</i>	518
Exploring the practicalities and processes of developing a collaborative group space in a platform for text mining: Gale Digital Scholar Lab <i>Ketchley, Sarah; Bowden, Rebecca</i>	519
Few Shot Classification for Labeling of Medieval and Early Modern Charter Texts <i>Kovács, Tamás; Aoun, Sandy; Vogeler, Georg; Nicolaou, Angelos; Luger, Daniel; Atzenhofer-Baumgartner, Florian; Lammingner, Florian; Decker, Franziska</i>	520
FigureOut - Automatic Detection of Metaphors in Hebrew Across the Eras <i>Münz-Manor, Ophir; Toker, Michael; Mishali, Oren; Kimmelfeld, Benny; Belinkov, Yonatan; Cohen, Adir</i>	521
Fostering a Culture of Inclusive and Fair Open Science Infrastructure in the Asia Pacific <i>Akashi, Eliko; Miyakita, Goki; Okawa, Keiko</i>	522
From a single-use script to a reusable Python package: assisting researchers in creating FAIR software <i>van Boheemen, Jelte; Baarda, Tijmen Christiaan</i>	524
GitMA Poster <i>Meister, Malte; Gerstorfer, Dominik; Schumacher, Mareike Katharina; Gius, Evelyn</i>	525
Gloss-ViBe: Early Medieval Glosses and the Digital Humanities <i>Bauer, Bernhard</i>	526
History as a visual concept: editing Peter of Poitiers' "Compendium historiae in genealogia Christi" <i>Bleier, Roman; Cleaver, Laura; Fischer, Franz; Sahle, Patrick; Worm, Andrea; Krottmaier, Sina; Macchiarelli, Agnese; Cugliana, Elisa; Goerss, Eleanor; Streicher, Maria; Rouxel, Lennart</i>	527
How to be flexible - OpenAtlas as Highly Adaptable Database Software in the Scope of Digital Humanities <i>Watzinger, Alexander; Koschiček-Krombholz, Bernhard; Olschnögger, Andreas; Hoffmann, Christoph; Großfurtner, Moritz</i>	528
How to detect institutional and regional feature clusters in late medieval charters? Collaboration between more and less digital humanists in the project BeCoRe <i>Barret, Sébastien; Helias-Baron, Marlène; Stutzmann, Dominique; Tscherne, Niklas; Vogeler, Georg; Schindler, Jacqueline</i>	529
I-Analyzer: a flexible interface for full-text search, filtering and visualization <i>Janssen, Berit; Stiphout, Mees; van der Plas, Luka</i>	531
"... ich würde keinen Teufel schonen, möcht' er laborieren oder kollaborieren" – Jean Paul's Letters as Data for Various Research Domains in the Context of the National Research Data Infrastructure Text+ <i>Neuber, Frederike; Hug, Marius; Wiegand, Frank</i>	532
Index of Middle English Prose: A search tool based on language modelling <i>Honkapohja, Alpo; Thaisen, Jacob; Nøklestad, Anders</i>	533
Interchangeability of ngrams models between heterogeneous dataset. <i>Cuper, Mirjam</i>	534
iPBL – supplementing literary bibliography with internet sources. Collaborative cataloguing <i>Koper, Beata; Rosiński, Cezary; Wachek, Barbara; Maryl, Maciej; Umerle, Tomasz</i>	535
It's not in the text: creating meaning through graph-based digital commentaries <i>Carloni, Massimiliano</i>	536

Kaleidoscopic Patterns of Protest: Qualifying and Quantifying Visual and Textual (Self-)Representations in Eastern European Protest Cultures	
<i>Howanitz, Gernot; Kaltseis, Magdalena</i>	538
Large Language Models and NER: better results with less work	
<i>Thalken, Rosamond Elizabeth; Wilkens, Matthew; Mimno, David</i>	539
Leading collaborative research on video corpora. CANEVAS tools and methods.	
<i>Tessier, Laurent; Bourgatte, Michael</i>	540
Learning from the Experts On-Site: A Short Term Digital Humanities Study Abroad Framework	
<i>Mapes, Kristen</i>	542
Let data sing the Uyghur Twelve Muqam: A text mining on lyrics	
<i>Kai, Limai; Yang, Zekun; Feng, Huiling; Liu, Yuenan; Liang, Jihong; Yang, Huilin; Yan, Jin; Huang, Yanfen; Guan, Kongwen</i>	542
Linked Open Data for Tibetan-Himalayan Researchers: Opportunities for Collaboration in User Experience Studies	
<i>Mapp, Rennie; Gunn, Stan; Shinozaki, Yuji; Montano, Andres</i>	546
Linking Epic Speeches	
<i>Forstall, Christopher W.; Stagg, Wyatt</i>	547
Mapping the (Digital) Linguistic Atlas of Scotland	
<i>Pluschkovits, Markus; Kirk, John</i>	548
Meet PUDEL – A New Service for Sharing and Documenting Data Models	
<i>Becker, Anja; Graiff, Cecilia; Goldhahn, Dirk; Kretschmer, Uwe; Mühleder, Peter; Naether, Franziska</i>	549
MEHDIE: The Middle East Heritage Data Integration Endeavor	
<i>Rusinek, Sinai; Sagi, Tomer; Zaga, Moran; Lev, Efraim; Moshe, Lavee</i>	551
MemoRekall-IIIF, an open source and versatile web application for video and digital document annotation	
<i>Hart, Jacob; Bardiou, Clarisse; Rouquet, David</i>	552
Metadata Enrichment in the Living with Machines Project: User-focused Collaborative Database Development in a Digital Humanities Context	
<i>Westerling, Kalle; Beavan, David; Beelen, Kaspar; Coll Ardanuy, Mariona; Hobson, Timothy; Last, Christina; Pedrazzini, Nilo; Reese, Griffith; Luke, Hare</i>	553
Modeling Prototypicality and Uncertainty in Genre Concepts	
<i>Schroeter, Julian</i>	555
More than Meets the (Artificial) Eye: Exploring Historical Photographs from Ireland with Computer Vision Methods	
<i>Osti, Giulia; Cushing, Amber; Little, Suzanne</i>	556
Named Entity Recognition for a Text-Based Catalog of Ancient Greek Authors and Works	
<i>Berti, Monica</i>	557
Named Entity Recognition in Pre-modern Arabic Biographical Texts	
<i>Ishida, Yuri; Baba, Kensuke; Baba, Takahiro</i>	558
Nineteenth-century adaptations of concert music for domestic use as seen in contemporary periodicals: digital scholarship built on the foundations of IIIF, MEI and Linked Data	
<i>Lewis, David; Page, Kevin R</i>	559
Normative texts in the City-State of Bern (1528-1795). Testing a Simple Knowledge Organisation System (SKOS) and Automatic Meta Data on a Handwritten Corpus. Normative texts in the City-State of Bern (1528-1795).	
<i>Romein, C. Annemieke; Veldhoen, Sara</i>	560
Open Research Practices with the OntoME-Geovistory environment	
<i>Alamercery, Vincent; Beretta, Francesco; Favey, François-Joseph; Ferhod, Djamel; Knecht, David; Muck, Gaétan; Perraud, Alexandre; Pica, Morgane; Schneider, Jonas; Stebler, Andreas</i>	561
OstData – Building a Research Data Service for Enabling Interdisciplinarity and Regional Collaboration in Central, East, and Southeast European Studies	
<i>Frank, Ingo</i>	562
<i>Our Heritage, Our Stories: Democratising the UK national collection</i>	
<i>Hannaford, Ewan David; Alexander, Marc; Hughes, Lorna; Lewis, Rhiannon</i>	565
Pandore: a toolbox for digital humanities text-based workflows	
<i>Abrahabi, Motasem; Fedchenko, Valentina; Petkovic, Ljudmila; Roe, Glenn</i>	566
Preserving the Early Born-Digital Heritage of Floppy Disk Magazines	
<i>Roeder, Torsten; Herbst, Yannik; Leitgeb, Johannes; Marenc, Madlin; Shtohryn, Tomash</i>	567
Publication networks in Romanian-German journals	
<i>Dobbener, Sofie</i>	569
Quick TEI (QTEI) - a lightweight tool for TEI documents	
<i>Schepp, Moritz; Wübbena, Thorsten</i>	570
Revisiting connotations of digital humanists: Exploration based on semi-structured interviews and survey	
<i>Ma, Rongqian</i>	571

(Re)Visual(izing) Archive Southeastern Europe: A data model and interface redesign <i>Galka, Selina; Sagadin, Suzana; Scholger, Martina</i>	572
Saving Ukrainian Cultural Heritage Online: Responsive Emergency DH at Scale <i>Dombrowski, Quinn; Kijas, Anna; Rakityanskaya, Anna; Wingate, Alex</i>	573
SemanaHD. Bringing together the Latin American digital humanities community <i>Priani Saiso, Ernesto; Afanador, Maria José; Del Rio Riande, Gimena</i>	574
Sibiriana: designing a platform for aggregation of the historical and cultural heritage of the Angara-Yenisei macroregion <i>Volodin, Andrey; Senotrusova, Polina; Antamoshkin, Oleslav; Kizhner, Inna; Rumyantzev, Maksim; Pikov, Nikita; Gruzdev, Andrey</i>	575
Syllab – software for semi-automatic stylometric analysis for poetry <i>Rykowska, Aleksandra</i>	576
TEITOK API - Programmable DH Corpora <i>Janssen, Maarten</i>	577
The COVID-19 pandemic in two Austrian media corpora: methods, analyses, and examples from a lexical and a morpho-pragmatic perspective <i>Dorn, Amelie; Korecky-Kröll, Katharina; Ziegler, Theresa; Höll, Jan; Lenz, Alexandra N.</i>	578
The European Literary Text Collection in TextGrid Repository <i>Rißler-Pipka, Nanette; Calvo Tello, José; Funk, Stefan E.; Odebrecht, Carolin; Schöch, Christof; Veentjer, Ubbo</i>	579
The Journal of Computational Literary Studies (JCLS): Community, review, and editorial workflow in an Open Access Journal <i>Gius, Evelyn; Schöch, Christof; Trilcke, Peer; Gerstorfer, Dominik; Guhr, Svenja; Ripoll, Elodie; Shlyter-Gäthje, Henry</i>	581
The networked edition humboldt digital <i>Dumont, Stefan; Kraft, Tobias; Thomas, Christian</i>	583
The Social Sciences and Humanities Open Marketplace: contextualising digital resources in a registry <i>Barbot, Laure; Battaner Moro, Elena; Buddenbohm, Stefan; Concordia, Cesare; Dolinar, Maja; Đurčo, Matej; Gray, Edward; Grisot, Cristina; Illmayer, Klaus; Kirnbauer, Martin; Kleemola, Mari; König, Alexander; Kurzmeier, Michael; McGillivray, Barbara; Parente Boavida, Clara; Schuster, Christian; Vipavc Brvar, Irena; Wnuk, Magdalena</i>	584
The use of digital tools for the characterisation of archaeological sites by surface archaeological survey <i>Tobalina-Pulido, Leticia</i>	586
The Yugoslavian Interwar Business Network <i>Evkoski, Bojan; Lazarević, Žarko; Pančur, Andrej; Fišer, Darja</i>	586
Three Is the Charm: A New Architecture, New Features and New Projects in EVT 3 <i>Bioglio, Livio; Cerretini, Giacomo; D'Agostino, Giulia; Magnanti, Elisabetta; Rosselli Del Turco, Roberto</i>	589
Toward establishing the standard digital public history framework: information platform for Japanese historical materials <i>Kameda, Akihiro; Goto, Makoto</i>	590
Towards a common data model for semantic annotation of digital media: A new FOSS toolchain <i>Rossenova, Lozana; Sohmen, Lucia; Duchesne, Paul; Günther, Lukas; Schubert, Zoe; Bluemel, Ina</i>	592
Towards a datafication of Antwerp street life? Co-creating a dataset of 100.000+ pages of handwritten police reports (1876-1945) <i>Lefranc, Lith</i>	593
Towards Building an Infrastructure to Keeping Alive and Conveying the Memories of Victims of Nazi Persecution <i>Jänicke, Stefan</i>	594
Towards Diachronic Corpus of Polish Latin <i>Marszałek, Jagoda; Nowak, Krzysztof; Krawczyk, Iwona</i>	595
UK Digital Comics: Challenges and Opportunities of a Collaborative Doctoral Partnership. A Co-designed Comic Poster <i>Priego, Ernesto; Berube, Linda; de la Mora, Francisco; Cooke, Ian; Makri, Stephann; Wisdom, Stella</i>	596
Using Digital Tools to Create Modern Multi-Search Engine for Polish Historical Dictionaries <i>Rodek, Ewa</i>	598
Using text summarization models to improve digital reading of scientific papers <i>Mastrobattista, Ludovica; Alrahabi, Motasem; Fedchenko, Valentina; Jomaa, Oussama; Gawley, James; Cordova, Johanna; Roe, Glenn</i>	598
Visualizing connections between Egypt and Southern Levant, using mapping and network analysis. <i>Filimonov, Evgenia; Kizhner, Inna; Ben-Dor Evian, Shirley; Bar-Oz, Guy</i>	600
VR in the Classroom: From Immersion Experiences to Creating 360° Video <i>Renner, Max; Evans, Sarah; Applegate, Matt</i>	602
WebChamame: An Online Tool for Morphological Analysis of Various Historical Japanese Texts using UniDic Dictionaries <i>Ogiso, Toshinobu; Tsutsumi, Tomoaki</i>	603

Werner Kofler radio plays - 2 audio editions and their dissemination	
<i>Raunig, Elisabeth; Klug, Helmut W.</i>	605
Where do they go? 10 years of professional choices by Digital Humanities Masters graduates (and what we might learn from them)	
<i>Edmond, Jennifer</i>	606
Workflows for Innovative Scholarly Outputs in Social Sciences and Humanities	
<i>Maryl, Maciej; Błaszczyńska, Marta</i>	607
20 Years of Digital Medievalist – A Reflection on the Development of a Community	
<i>Bleier, Roman; Borek, Luise; Campagnolo, Alberto; Fischer, Franz; Gengnagel, Tessa; Hodel, Tobias</i>	608

Appendix

Author Index	610
--------------------	-----

nal Conference on Document Analysis and Recognition (ICDAR), 2017, pp. 19-24, doi: 10.1109/ICDAR.2017.307.

Nockels J, Gooding P, Ames S, Terras M. Understanding the application of handwritten text recognition technology in heritage contexts: a systematic review of Transkribus in published research. *Arch Sci (Dordr)*. 2022;22(3):367-392. doi: 10.1007/s10502-022-09397-0. Epub 2022 Jun 17. PMID: 35730063; PMCID: PMC9205146.

van der Sijs, N. (2019). De krant hoorde erbij. *Geschiedenis Magazine*, 3, 37-40.

Ströbel P, Clematide S, Improving OCR of black letter in historical newspapers: the unreasonable effectiveness of HTR models on low-resolution images. Paper presented at Digital Humanities 2019, Zurich. https://www.zora.uzh.ch/id/eprint/177164/1/Improving_OCR_of_Black_Letter_in_Historical_Newspapers_The_Unreasonable_Effecti.pdf

Crowdsourcing in History. New participatory and inclusive methodological challenges for research in History in Spain (CrowdHistory)

Bocanegra Barbecho, Lidia

lbocanegra@go.ugr.es
Universidad de Granada, Spain

Ortega Santos, Antonio

aortegas@ugr.es
Universidad de Granada

The Project:

The main objective of CrowdHistory project¹ is to identify, analyse, test and standardise methodological practices of citizen participation in Spanish R&D projects from the perspective of Digital Humanities, both within and outside the academic field.

State of the Art

The current state of research lacks scientific investigations that reflect methodologically and conceptually on public participation in historical research in Spain. When we talk about public participation in research, we refer to Citizen Science (CS): this is scientific research coordinated by scientists in which ordinary people, amateur and non-professional researchers, participate in some aspect of the research (Eitzel 2017). This type of methodological research is practically new in the humanities; however, there are a discrete number of research projects that use CS that are currently underway or have already been carried out, which offer a suitable breeding ground with relevant data to carry out analyses in Citizen Science (Bocanegra et al. 2017).

This citizen participatory aspect is one of the main characteristics of the Digital Humanities (DH) (Bocanegra 2020); in the last decade there has been a change in the way of doing research in the human sciences as society begins to have a participatory role

during the research process; beyond being the subject of analysis to even participate in part or all stages of scientific production.

This new way of doing science is strongly driven by the growing boom of web 2.0 and, within it, digital social networks stand out as a place for interaction (Bocanegra 2020); betting on collective intelligence (Surowiecki 2004) and micro-participation.

Methodological Framework:

To achieve the proposed objectives, CrowdHistory implements a four-phase methodology as follow:

- Phase 1 - Detection of research projects in history that use public participation from citizen science. Design and structuring of a relational web database (DB), implemented through the Drupal Content Management System, version 9, PHP 7 and MariaDB 5.5. The established database (DB) allows classification parameters in closed lists and with free text fields, where explanatory information about the strategies of approaching the public has been added.

- Phase 2 - Standardisation methodology on public participation in historical research. This phase will lead to first analyses and, as a result, to a first cataloguing of participatory processes (of citizen involvement) as well as engagement activities (public engagement).

- Phase 3 - Testing and improving the methodology of public participation in historical research from citizen science through pilot cases. use of hybrid (physical/digital) citizen laboratories where some of the classified participatory approaches and techniques will be put into practice.

- Phase 4 - Evaluation of the public participation and public engagement methodology and development of good practice guidelines.

We have now completed phases 1 and 2 and are implementing phase 3.

Preliminary results:

Currently, we have identified and classified 458 international projects that use CS through the project's web database: <https://cohistoria.es/>; of which 161 are Spanish initiatives or with Spanish participation². Data collection continues as new initiatives are found.

An ad hoc classification has been made on the basis of two models: PPS – *Public Participation Strategies* and PES – *Public Engagement Strategies*, through which a series of participatory and public engagement activities have been identified, respectively.

PPS activities identified:

Data enrichment / Data entry (metadata)

Tagging/Classification (social tagging)

Geolocation

Source collection

Historical recreation

Transcription / text editing

Transfer knowledge

PES activities identified:

Social networks / Web

Living labs (living labs)

Institutional communication channels (distribution lists)

Cultural performance

The PPS model has been built by bringing together the CS approaches defined by Bonney (1999) and Simon (2010): Contributive, Collaborative, Co-created and Hosted (see Figure 1).

PPS MODEL

Public Participation Strategies

CONTRIBUTIVE

Project generally designed by scientists and where the public mainly contributes with data

COLLABORATIVE

Usually designed by scientists and for which members of the public not only contribute data, but can also help refine the project design, analyse the data or disseminate the results

CO-CREATED

Designed by scientists and members of the public, working together, at least some of the public participants are actively involved in most or all stages of the scientific process

HOSTED

Projects in which the institution provides part of its facilities, or resources, to present programmes developed and implemented by public groups or occasional visitors.

Citizen Science / Citizen Humanities

Figure 1: PPS Model.

Through the first analysis of the data obtained in CrowdHistory, we observe that the vast majority of the registered projects use more than one participatory approach. In general, contributive and collaborative participation are the most used. The explanation for this result is most likely due to the ease of implementation of these two approaches, as practitioners/scientists have greater control over these participatory processes, relying on small or medium-scale contributions on digital platforms. This versatility of digital, and of leaving a small or medium-sized part of the research process open to the public, at the level of contributing data or objects, is what accelerates the participatory process and also brings important benefits.

Regarding the PPS activities, the majority of the classified initiatives involve more than one main participatory activity, being Data Enrichment/Data Entry and Source Collection the predominant ones, with the use of these two activities together being very common (see Figure 2³ and 3⁴ for examples).

Archivo Contra la pared
Participatory approaches and activities: Source Collection | Enrichment/Data Entry | Contributive

Archivo Contra la pared is a digital archive made up of documents (posters, pamphlets, stickers, etc.) produced by political and social collectives and initiatives in the city of Seville, from 1978 to the present day: neighbourhood movements, ecologists, anti-militarists, student movements, feminist movements, workers' movements and trade unions, left-wing political parties, citizen platforms, etc. Citizens are invited to contribute photographic archives, or photographers (professional or amateur) to photograph original posters in their possession or on the public highway.

Developed by **Tramalló**: association located in Seville.

Patrimonio herido
Participatory approaches and activities: Enrichment/Data Entry | Geolocation | Transfer Knowledge | Collaborative

Project developed by the **iArthis_LAB** research group from the **University of Malaga**. It implements mechanisms that facilitate the direct participation of citizens in the care of cultural heritage. Interested parties are invited to participate in training processes for the detection of heritage deterioration, which must be recorded through photographs and descriptions.

Archivo histórico del Partido Comunista. Colección Digital Complutense
Participatory approaches and activities: Social Tagging | Contributive

The photographic collection relating to the Civil War of the **Archivo Histórico del PCE** consists of approximately 3,200 photographs and some 2,000 negatives. From the collection of negatives, there is a set of almost 1,300 images, of which around 800 have been digitalised in this collection. It allows the tagging of photographs by any person (social tagging). Digitalisation project carried out by the Library of the **Universidad Complutense de Madrid**.

Generaciones de Plata
Participatory approaches and activities: Enrichment/Data Entry | Source collection | Contributive

Project developed by the **University of Granada** through the **Desgbre Foundation**. The initiative combines research and dissemination to bring to Andalusian society the figure of scientists who disappeared, went into exile and/or were repressed during the period of the Civil War and the following years.

The public is invited to contribute data (via a web form), archives and information about Andalusian scientists who were repressed during Franco's dictatorship.

Figure 2. Examples of Spanish projects using Citizen Science.

Archivo histórico del Partido Comunista. Colección Digital Complutense
Participatory approaches and activities: Social Tagging | Contributive

The photographic collection relating to the Civil War of the **Archivo Histórico del PCE** consists of approximately 3,200 photographs and some 2,000 negatives. From the collection of negatives, there is a set of almost 1,300 images, of which around 800 have been digitalised in this collection. It allows the tagging of photographs by any person (social tagging). Digitalisation project carried out by the Library of the **Universidad Complutense de Madrid**.

Generaciones de Plata
Participatory approaches and activities: Enrichment/Data Entry | Source collection | Contributive

Project developed by the **University of Granada** through the **Desgbre Foundation**. The initiative combines research and dissemination to bring to Andalusian society the figure of scientists who disappeared, went into exile and/or were repressed during the period of the Civil War and the following years.

The public is invited to contribute data (via a web form), archives and information about Andalusian scientists who were repressed during Franco's dictatorship.

Figure 3. Examples of Spanish projects using Citizen Science.

In the case of Spain, we have identified and catalogued a set of "mother" disciplines of the mapped initiatives. The results show that the discipline of History is in first position, followed by disciplines such as Archaeology, Museography and Heritage, as well as Digital Humanities and Arts (Figure 4). It should be noted that the initiatives that use participatory processes in their implementation are usually inter- or multidisciplinary based; and this is due to the very characteristic of citizen science as it is fed by the different knowledge of the people who collaborate. Likewise, most of these catalogued projects carry out public participation in an on-line way in which individuals contribute data or objects; in this mode, the technical/digital process is very important, therefore the project is developed from a specific area of study that is supported, at least methodologically, in other areas such as ICT.

Figure 4. Disciplines identified.

Notes

1. This poster is part of the R&D project / PID2020-117619RB-I00, funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033/
2. Data obtained as of April 28, 2023. The classification and data entry procedure will continue throughout the implementation of the entire project as we come across new initiatives.
3. Archivo contra la Pared: <https://cohistoria.es/proyectos/archivo-contra-la-pared> (Project website: <https://www.facebook.com/archivocontralapared>). Patrimonio Herido: <https://cohistoria.es/proyectos/patrimonio-herido>(Project website: https://patrimonioherido.iarthislab.eu/en_US/home/).
4. Archivo Histórico del Partido Comunista de España: <https://cohistoria.es/proyectos/archivo-historico-del-partido-comunista-de-espana>(Project website: <https://webs.ucm.es/BUCM/atencion//17952.php>) https://patrimonioherido.iarthislab.eu/en_US/home/). Generaciones de Plata: <https://cohistoria.es/proyectos/generaciones-de-plata>(Project website: <https://generacionesdeplata.fundaciondescubre.es/>)

Bibliography

Eitzel, M. V. / Cappadonna, J. L. / Santos-Lang, C. / Duerr, R. E. / Virapongse, A. / West, S. E. / Jiang, Q. (2017). "Citizen Science Terminology Matters: Exploring Key Terms", in: *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice*, 2(1), 1: 1-20. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5334/cstp.96>.

Bocanegra Barbecho, L. / Toscano, M. / Delgado Anés, L. (2017): "Co-creación, participación y redes sociales para hacer historia. Ciencia con y para la sociedad", in *Historia y Comunicación Social*, Vol. 22-2: 325 – 346. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5209/HICS.57847>.

Bocanegra Barbecho, L. (2020): "Ciencia ciudadana y memoria histórica: nuevas perspectivas historiográficas desde las Humanidades Digitales y la Historia Pública Digital", in: Caro, Jorge / Díaz-de la Fuente, Silvia / Ahedo, Virginia / Zurro, Débora / Madella, Marco / Galán, José M. / Izquierdo, Luis R. / Santos, José Ignacio / Del Olmo, Ricardo (eds.): *Terra Incognita: Libro blanco sobre transdisciplinariedad y nuevas formas de investigación en el Sistema Español de Ciencia y Tecnología*, Burgos: PressBooks. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4046754>.

Bonney, R. (1999): *Public Participation in Scientific Research: Defining the Field and Assessing Its Potential for Informal Science Education. A Caise Inquiry Group Report*. Washington, D.C.: Center for Advancement of Informal Science Education (Caise). 1-58 <https://www.informalscience.org/sites/default/files/PublicParticipationinScientificResearch.pdf> [30.04.2023].

Simon, N. (2010): *The Participatory Museum*, Santa Cruz de California: Museum 2.0.

Surowiecki, J. (2004); *The Wisdom of Crowds*, New York: Doubleday.

Cuban digital collections: an approach for collaboration and innovation.

Terrón Quintero, Grisel

griseluna@gmail.com
Oficina del Historiador de la ciudad de la Habana, Cuba

Guerra Figueredo, Eritk

eritk.guerra@gmail.com
Oficina del Historiador de la ciudad de la Habana, Cuba

Solernou Ferrer, Alaina

alASF11@gmail.com
Oficina del Historiador de la ciudad de la Habana, Cuba

Echarri Ramirez, Bryan

ginnkagura10@gmail.com
Oficina del Historiador de la ciudad de la Habana, Cuba

The Office of the Historian of the City of Havana (OHCH) is a Cuban public cultural institution, founded in 1938. It is in charge of managing the 500-year-old cultural heritage of the Historic Center. Since its founding, the welfare of citizens and visitors has been its main focus of work, and culture among its main pillars. To achieve its goals, OHCH is developing a digital transformation plan based on smart city concepts. "The transformation of a city into a smart city should aim to improve the quality of life of the people who use it, both residents and visitors." (Chorabi et al, 2012)

The proposed poster will show one of the results of this digital transformation plan: the OHCH digital collection management system. Based on Omeka (www.omeka.org) it is available at <https://coleccionedigitales.ohc.cu>.

COLECCIONES DIGITALES

CONTACTANOS
✉ coleccionedigitales@ohc.cu

VISÍTANOS
🌐 coleccionedigitales.ohc.cu

Brindamos la posibilidad de acceder a nuestros valores de manera universal e integrada.

Logos: OHCH, Universidad de la Habana, DICH

It is a virtual space where digital objects are produced and managed from the digitization of the analog collections of Cuban memory institutions. Its main purpose is to provide universal and collaborative access to our cultural wealth, even when for various reasons it is not exhibited in our heritage institutions or is dispersed. It also allows to reproduce, in a standardized way, the relationships between all these objects and between them and the visitors.

The development of this digital tool is part of the International Cooperation project called "The Historic Center of Havana, towards a smart city model" funded by the European Union and the City Council of Barcelona. It has also received the contribution and experience derived from the Humboldt Digital Project (ProHD), developed by the OHCH and the Berlin-Brandenburg Academy of Sciences. ProHD focuses on knowledge exchange in the field of Digital Humanities. It has provided the OHCH with a methodology and theoretical body that has enabled the implementation of a workflow that yields the expected results. OHCH Digital Collections responds to the need to cover the cultural dimension that involves the processes of identification of citizens with their heritage, their environment and the creation of a collective memory.

Author Index

Abdul-Rahman, Alfie	427
Abo Bakir Shuan, Yasmin Hawar	326
Abraham, Vijoy	481
Adachi, Airu	507
Adamou, Alessandro	151
Afanador, Maria José	574
Akashi, Eliko	522
Alaasam, Reem	201
Alamercery, Vincent	561
Alassi, Sepideh	128, 148
Aledavood, Parham	158
Alex, Beatrice	267
Alexander, Eric	43
Alexander, Marc	565
Algee-Hewitt, Mark Andrew	166
Alliata, Giacomo	86
Almohamad, Adnan	468
Alrahabi, Motasem	154, 566, 598
Alvares Freire, Fernanda	400
Alvite-Díez, María-Luisa	84
Ammann, Nora Olivia	148
Andresen, Melanie	180
Andrews, Tara Lee	321
Angelis, Stavros	115
Angermeier, Jan	315
Antamoshkin, Oleslav	575
Antoniak, Maria	463
Aoun, Sandy	171, 508, 520
Applegate, Matt	402, 602
Arnold, Eckhart	112
Arnold, Taylor	239
Arthur, Paul	222
Atanassova, Rossitza	505
Atzenhofer-Baumgartner, Florian	171, 508, 520
Aubert, Olivier	95
Aurich, Jens	494
Azizifard, Narges	150
Baarda, Tijmen Christiaan	524
Baba, Kensuke	558
Baba, Takahiro	558
Babbar, Rohit	425
Bach, Benjamin	267
Backman, Agnieszka	461
Baillot, Anne	iv
Baker, James	478
Bal, Jakob	176
Baldi, Alberto	177
Bar-Oz, Guy	600
Barbot, Laure	31, 584
Bardiot, Clarisse	120, 127, 552
Barker, Elton	351, 467
Barret, Sébastien	529
Bathurst, Taylor	367
Battle Baró, Sabina	337
Battaner Moro, Elena	31, 584
Bauer, Bernhard	526
Beavan, David	553
Becker, Anja	549
Beelen, Kaspar	408, 553
Beerens, Rudy Jos	313
Behret, Marius	281
Bei der Wieden, Gesa	367
Beier, Mirijam	510
Belinkov, Yonatan	521
Bell, Peter	141
Belouin, Pascal	147
Ben-Dor Evian, Shirley	600
Benedetti, Andrea	319
Beresford, Andrew M.	159
Beretta, Francesco	561
Bermúdez Sabel, Helena	121
Bernadou, Agiatis	67
Bernardi, Joanne	438
Bernasconi, Valentine	169
Berti, Monica	557
Berube, Linda	596
Bhattacharyya, Sayan	153
Bhaugeerutty, Aruna	516
Bioglio, Livio	589
Birkholz, Julie M.	496
Bishop, David	464
Bizzoni, Yuri	404
Bleier, Roman	205, 527, 608
Blickhan, Samantha	92
Blin, Irénée	127
Blotière, Emilie	243
Bludau, Mark-Jan	43
Bluemel, Ina	592
Blumtritt, Jonathan	270
Blundell, Jon	451
Bocanegra Barbecho, Lidia	501
Bode, Katherine	392
Boerner, Ingo	293
Bonch-Osmolovskaya, Anastasia	288
Bonnet, Tyler	517
Bonora, Paolo	202
Boot, Peter	389
Booth, Alison	416
Bordalejo, Barbara	285
Borek, Luise	50, 442, 608
Borek, Arkadiusz	156
Borges, Rebekka	331
Borst, Janos	365
Bourgatte, Michael	540
Bowden, Rebecca	519
Boyd, Adriane	36
Bradley, Adam	43
Bradley, John	458
Brando, Carmen	233
Breitfuss, Gert	243
Broadwell, Peter	481
Broeder, Daan	51
Brosens, Koenraad	313
Brottrager, Judith	372
Broun, Dauvit	458
Brown, Susan	25, 48, 287
Browne, Jeremy	196
Buarque, Bernardo	135
Budak, Nick	37, 325
Budak, Nicholas Andrew	219
Buddenbohm, Stefan	31, 584
Buehler, Axel	256
Burge, Caitlin Rose	308
Burghardt, Manuel	197, 357, 365, 432
Burr, Elisabeth	102

Burrows, Vera	29	Cupar, Drahomira	51, 243
Bursztajn-Illingworth, Zoe	29	Cuper, Mirjam	534
Butterworth, Alex	318, 468	Cushing, Amber	556
Byrne, Aidan	99	Cuthbertson, Galen	392
Byszuk, Joanna	40, 59, 461, 496	Cvrček, Václav	323
Börner, Ingo	125, 496, 513	Czmiel, Alexander	490
Błaszczczyńska, Marta	307, 607	Dahiya, Vasundhra	295
Cafiero, Florian	266	Dahiya, Lavanya	295
Calderon Reyes, Emilio	299	Damerow, Julia	45, 466
Calvo Tello, José	579	Das, Madhurima	115
Campagnolo, Alberto	608	David, Kelly	516
Camps, Jean-Baptiste	162, 207	Davoury, Baudouin	349
Cantareira, Gabriel Dias	427	De Bastiani, Chiara	492
Cappellotto, Anna	93	de Bonth, Roland	500
Cardoso, Bruno	313	de Does, Jesse	500
Carine, Mark	456	de Günther, Sabine	409
Carlino, Carola	35	de Jong, Ruud	500
Carloni, Massimiliano	139, 536	de la Mora, Francisco	596
Casaretto, Antje	105	de Prekel, Inez	313
Casties, Robert	45, 466	de Smedt, Koenraad	453
Cerretini, Giacomo	589	Debbeler, Anke	331
Chadha, Aanya	295	Decker, Franziska	171, 508, 520
Chagué, Alix	73, 142, 349	Dejaeghere, Tess	496
Chambers, Sally	67, 496	Del Grosso, Angelo Mario	132
Champagne, Ashley	168	Del Rio Riande, Gimena	574
Charlesworth, Ellen	159	Dello Buono, Martina	202
Charlton, Ash	123	Delmas-Glass, Emmanuelle	517
Charvat, Vera Maria	125, 496	Dennerlein, Katrin	181
Chattopadhyay, Sudipta	78	Depuydt, Katrien	499
Che, Qun	340	Dershowitz, Nachum	256
Chen, Sixing	178	di Lenardo, Isabella	411
Chen, Shih-Pei	340	Di Pasquale, Alessio	393
Chen, You-Jun	362	Dias, Renata	279
Chen, Anne	468	Dickmann, Lars	38
Chen, Jing	473, 484	Disch, Leonie	243
Chevalier, Cécile	448	Doat, Soline	349
Christen, Alessio	319	Dobbener, Sofie	569
Cinková, Silvie	323, 496	Dolinar, Maja	31, 584
Ciotti, Fabio	177	Dombrowski, Quinn	51, 442, 453, 461, 573
Cipolla, Maria Adele	93	Donnay, Michael	440
Ciula, Arianna	45, 440	Dorn, Amelie	578
Ciula, Ariana	458	Downie, J. Stephen	110
Cleaver, Laura	527	Drobac, Senka	90
Clement, Tanya	29, 292	Du, Keli	178
Clérice, Thibault	73, 142, 349	Duan, Tinghui	60
Cohen, Evyatar	77	Dubnicek, Ryan	381
Cohen, Evan Gary	77	Duchesne, Paul	592
Cohen, Adir	521	Dudar, Julia	496, 513
Colavizza, Giovanni	446	Dumont, Stefan	104, 583
Cole, Nicholas	427	Dupertuis, Didier	310
Coleman, Catherine Nicole	174	Dupont, Yoann	154
Coll Ardanuy, Marion	553	Durco, Matej	125
Collinson, Alwyn	515	Đurčo, Matej	31, 496, 584
Concordia, Cesare	31, 584	Dähne, Janis	429
Constantopoulos, Panos	246	Diez-Platas, Fátima	84
Cooke, Ian	597	Diez-Platas, M ^a Luisa	84
Cope, Jamie	451	Dörk, Marian	410
Cordova, Johanna	599	Dürfeld, Michael	278
Crawford, Cole	277, 466	D'Agostino, Giulia	589
Cremer, Fabian	488	E. Sinatra, Michael	158
Croxall, Brian	473	Echarri Ramirez, Bryan	503
Cugliana, Elisa	527	Eder, Maciej	496
Cumming, Julie	187	Edmond, Jennifer	140, 232, 440, 496, 606
Cummings, James	48, 119	Efer, Thomas	216

Eichert, Stefan	245	Gengnagel, Tessa	270, 608
El-Assady, Mennatallah	43	Gerstorfer, Dominik	71, 525, 581
el-Hajj, Hassan	151	Gheldof, Tom	468
El-Sana, Jihad	201	Ghosh, Sharanya	295
Elli, Tommaso	319	Gillikin Schoueri, Kelly	451
Enqvist, Johanna	90	Ginter, Filip	424
Ermolaev, Natalia	37, 325	Giovannetti, Francesca	202
Evalyn, Lawrence Isaac	361	Giovannini, Luca	513
Evans, Sarah	402, 602	Giovanola, Benedetta	252
Evkoski, Bojan	586	Gius, Evelyn	71, 213, 423, 525, 581
Fabbris, Giulia	493	Glawion, Anastasia	372
Fan, Tao	370	Goerss, Eleanor	527
Fanee, Mathieu	500	Goldhahn, Dirk	206, 550
Fantoli, Margherita	313	Gonzalez-Perez, Cesar	84
Faull, Katherine Mary	471	Gooding, Paul	254, 440
Faure, Margaux	349	Gordin, Shai	468
Favey, François-Joseph	561	Goto, Makoto	590
Fedchenko, Valentina	296, 566, 598	Goudin, Yoann	341
Feng, Huiling	543	Grabsch, Sascha	104
Fenlon, Katrina	273	Grace, Joshua	303
Ferger, Anne	400	Graffione, Cosetta	127
Ferhod, Djamel	561	Graiff, Cecilia	550
Fernandez, Claire	23	Gray, Edward	31, 584
Fernández Travieso, Carlota	84	Gray, Tanya	515
Ferrando, Stefania	127	Grigoriou, Dimitra	139
Ferraro, Ginestra	45	Grimmer, Jessica	274
Ferriter, Meghan	92	Grisot, Cristina	31, 584
Fileva, Evgeniia	496	Groes, Bas	99
Filimonov, Evgenia	600	Grossner, Karl	498
Finkelstein, Israel	256	Großfurtner, Moritz	245, 528
Fiormonte, Domenico	442	Gruber, Doris	184
Fischer, Anna	105	Gruzdev, Andrey	575
Fischer, Frank	293, 496, 513	Guan, Kongwen	543
Fischer, Franz	527, 608	Guerra, Eritk	260
Fitzpatrick, Richard	115	Guerra Figueredo, Eritk	503
Fišer, Darja	56, 67, 221, 587	Guhennec, Paul	310, 411
Flex, Valentina	119	Guhr, Svenja Simone	166
Flinn, Andrew	456	Guhr, Svenja	581
Foka, Anna	351	Gunn, Stan	546
Forest, Dominic	158	Gutiérrez De la Torre, Silvia E.	197
Forstall, Christopher W.	547	Günther, Lukas	592
Fox, Izzy	449	Haak, Candis	438
Frank, Ingo	562	Habring, Andreas	171
Freyberg, Linda	229, 409	Haedo, Anahi	233
Frissen, Thom	45	Hagen, Thora	418
Frontini, Francesca	59	Haider, Thomas Nikolaus	367
Frontoni, Emanuele	252, 383	Hampejs, Tomáš	359
Frühwirth, Timo	139	Hannaford, Ewan David	565
Fu, Yaming	190	Hardy, Kristine	204
Fubara-Manuel, Irene	448	Harnood, Juliya	291
Fucker, Selina	185	Hart, Jacob	127, 552
Fujinaga, Ichiro	187	Harvey, Peter	99
Funk, Stefan E.	579	Hastik, Canan	51
Futselaar, Ralf	305	Havens, Lucy	267
Fußbahn, Ulrike	103	Haverals, Wouter	322
Fyfe, Paul	225	Hay, Duncan	468
G S, Balu	485	Healey, Alexandra	119
Gagarina, Dinara	189	Heibi, Ivan	395
Galina Russel, Isabel	113	Heiden, Serge	346, 496
Galka, Selina	510, 572	Heinisch, Barbara	96
Garces, Juan	471	Heintzelman, Rebecca	291
Garnett, Vicky	496	Helias-Baron, Marlène	529
Gawley, James	598	Helling, Patrick	331
Gašparič, Jure	221	Hennicke, Steffen	147

Henning, Tim	197	Jänicke, Stefan	326, 420, 594
Henny-Krahmer, Ulrike	400, 490	K, Milja	425
Herbst, Yannik	567	Kai, Limai	542
Hergert, Katharina	372	Kaltseis, Magdalena	538
Herrmann, J. Berenike	59	Kameda, Akihiro	590
Heßbrüggen-Walter, Stefan	247	Kamocki, Paweł	453
Higgitt, Rebekah	318	Kamposiori, Christina	375
Hildebrand, Sébastien	127	Kane, Megan	160
Hill, Laurence	449	Karajgikar, Jajwalya	37
Hinrichs, Uta	43	Karlińska, Agnieszka	173, 217, 446
Hinzmann, Maria	60	Kasapaki, Mariaelena	246
Hirasawa, Kanako	507	Katakura, Shumpei	51
Hobson, Timothy	553	Katsikadeli, Christina	161
Hodel, Tobias	370, 384, 608	Kavčič, Alenka	221
Hoffmann, Christoph	245, 528	Keijzer, Carlijn	512
Hogg, Bennett	485	Kelly, Aodhán	45
Holler, Martin	171	Kenderdine, Sarah	22, 86
Honkapohja, Alpo	533	Kestemont, Mike	322
Horstmann, Jan	270	Ketchley, Sarah	519
Horvath, Aliz	69	Ketzan, Erik	418, 453
Horváth, Alíz	26	Khosmood, Foaad	303, 480
Hosker, Rachel	267	Kiesling, Brady	351
Hou, Yumeng	264	Kijas, Anna	573
Howanitz, Gernot	538	Kim, Jinah	277
Hsieh, Hsin-Yi	362	Kim, Yongsoo	436
Hu, Yuerong	110, 463	Kim, Hyounghun	436
Hu, Minghui	346	Kimmelfeld, Benny	521
Huang, Yanfen	543	Kinitz, Daniel	194, 216
Hubar, Patryk	217	Kirk, John	548
Hug, Marius	532	Kirnbauer, Martin	31, 585
Hughes, Alicia	455	Kirsten, Linda	260
Hughes, Lorna	565	Kiss, Børge	105
Humbel, Marco	455	Kitamoto, Asanobu	97
Humeau, Maxime	349	Kizhner, Inna	378, 575, 600
Hyvönen, Eero	91	Klaes, Christiane	446
Häußler, Julian	213	Klee, Anne	60
Höll, Jan	578	Kleemola, Mari	31, 585
Iliev, Dimitar	107	Kleinman, Scott	63
Illmayer, Klaus	31, 584	Kleymann, Rabea	146
Ilovan, Mihaela	48	Klug, Helmut W.	605
Impett, Leonardo	159, 250	Knecht, David	561
Inoue, Satoshi	144	Knorr, Charlotte	281
Inukai, Honami	507	Koeser, Rebecca Sutton	45, 466
Ishida, Yuri	558	Koho, Mikko	91
Jacquemin, Bernard	120	Konle, Leonard	301, 418
Jakacki, Diane	25, 119, 291	Konstanciak, Johanna	60
Jakacki, Diane Katherine	48, 473	Konstantinidou, Kyriaki	351
Janco, Andrew	36, 325	Koolen, Marijn	389
Janicki, Maciej	150	Koper, Beata	535
Jannidis, Fotis	301, 418	Korecky-Kröll, Katharina	578
Janssen, Maarten	323, 577	Korobzow, Natalie	105
Janssen, Berit	531	Koschicek-Krombholz, Bernhard	245
Jauhiainen, Heidi	87	Koschiček-Krombholz, Bernhard	528
Jauhiainen, Tommi	87	Koskowitz, Daniel	120
Jauhiainen, Iida	91	Koss, Max	338
Jeffrey, Evie	119	Koudoro-Parfait, Caroline	154
Jetka, Daniel	400, 490	Kovács, Tamás	171, 508, 520
Johnsen, Lars	489	Kraft, Tobias	260, 583
Johnson, Ian	119	Krauwer, Steven	67
Jomaa, Oussama	598	Krawczyk, Iwona	596
Jones, Cameron	480	Kremmel, Stefanie	518
Jouravel, Anna	112	Kretschmer, Uwe	550
Junginger, Pauline	478	Kretz, David	116
Juola, Patrick	40	Kreymer, Ilya	33

Krottmaier, Sina	527	Lin, Nungyao	340
Kruusmaa, Krister	272	Lin, Yu-Tung	362
Krušić, Lucija	124	Lindemann, David	446
Kryvenko, Anna	56	Lindquist, Thea	150
Kröger, Bärbel	57	Lingua, Andrea Maria	252
Kröncke, Merten	301	Linortner, Michael	214
Kubis, Marek	217	List, Ferdinand	278
Kunda, Bartłomiej	497	Little, Suzanne	556
Kunzmann, Markus	80	Liu, Guanwei	144
Kurzmeier, Michael	31, 89, 585	Liu, Yuenan	543
Kuzman Šlogar, Koraljka	195	Llewellyn, Clare	516
Kádár, Ákos	36	Losada Palenzuela, José Luis	398
Kåsen, Andre	489	Łubocki, Jakub	446
Kölligan, Daniel	105	Luengo, Pedro	84
König, Alexander	31, 585	Luger, Daniel	171, 508, 520
Königshofer, Elisabeth	491	Luke, Hare	553
Křen, Michal	323, 497	Lydon, Jane	222
La Mela, Matti	91	Ma, Rongqian	571
Labropoulou, Penny	446	Macchiarelli, Agnese	527
Laidlaw, Zoë	223	Maggetti, Daniel	319
Lalli, Roberto	118	Magnanti, Elisabetta	589
Lamminger, Florian	171, 508, 520	Mahony, Simon	190
Lamqaddam, Houda	313	Makri, Stephann	597
Landkammer, Miriam	214	Malínek, Vojtěch	445
Lang, Anouk	309, 461	Mandell, Laura	88
Lang, Sarah	442	Manna, Raffaele	35
Langeloh, Jacob	210	Mansutti, Sara	28
Langhanki, Florian	53	Mapes, Kristen	542
Langmead, Alison	473	Mapp, Rennie	42, 546
Lasch, Alexander	471	Marenc, Madlin	567
Lassche, Alie	333	Mariani, Fabio	338
Lassen, Ida Marie S.	404	Marienberg-Millikowsky, Itay	431
Lassner, David	37, 325	Marolt, Matija	221
Last, Christina	553	Marranca, Daniele	127
Laszkovits, Sabine	161, 497	Marshall, Catherine	196
Laszkovits, Sabine	125	Marszałek, Jagoda	595
Lavee, Moshe	378	Martens, Jeremy	223
Lavin, Matthew	463	Martin, Jonathan	83
Lawrence, Jon	408	Martin, Kim	287
Layne-Worthey, Glen	25, 110	Maryl, Maciej	173, 535, 607
Lazarević, Žarko	586	Massari, Arcangelo	395
LeBlanc, Zoe	64, 466	Mastrobattista, Ludovica	598
Lee, Ben	225	Matrone, Francesca	252
Lee, Jae-Yon	436	Mattei, Elena	336
Lefranc, Lith	593	Mauri, Michele	319, 406
Leguina, Adrian	99	Mayer, Sandra	139
Leitgeb, Johannes	567	Mazoue, Anaïs	349
Lejeune, Gaël	154	McDonough, Katherine	408, 468
Lendvai, Piroska	112	McGillivray, Barbara	31, 585
Lenz, Alexandra N.	578	McKay, Cory	187
Leontaridis, Panagiotis	246	Meindl, Martin	112
Leskinen, Petri	90	Meinecke, Christofer	326
Lev, Efraim	551	Meiorg, Marianne	504
Lewis, David	65, 559	Meister, Malte	71, 525
Lewis, Orly	468	Melby, Alan K.	196
Lewis, Rhiannon	565	Mellen, Pamela	45
Li, Jin	178, 482	Menassel, Mei	127
Li, Yi	328	Meneses, Luis	82
Li, Yongning	328	Menon, Nirmala	473
Li, Xiao	346	Mercer, Tom	99
Li, Huan	482	Merino Recalde, David	84
Liang, Jihong	543	Mertel, Adam	359
Liebl, Bernhard	432	Mertgens, Andreas	157
Liimatta, Aatu	424	Metilli, Daniele	443, 455

Michaan, Alexandre	120, 127	O'Connor, Thomas	115
Michalewicz, Nathan	499	O'Donnell, Daniel Paul	285
Middle, Sarah	318, 468	O'Sullivan, James	89, 473
Milio, Rachel	48	Oberreither, Bernhard	506
Miller, Dez Mary	160	Odebrecht, Carolin	579
Milling, Carsten	293, 513	Offert, Fabian	141, 250
Mimno, David	539	Ogawa, Jun	97, 451
Mishali, Oren	521	Ogiso, Toshinobu	234, 603
Miyakita, Goki	522	Ohge, Christopher	438, 478
Miyazaki, Hajime	144	Ohmukai, Ikki	51, 97, 507
Mochizuki, Ryo	51	Ohyama, Wataru	144
Montano, Andres	546	Okawa, Keiko	522
Monteleone, Cosimo	231	Olschnögger, Andreas	245, 528
Monti, Johanna	35	Orekhov, Boris	288
Moors, Sofie	100	Ortega Santos, Antonio	501
Moshe, Lavee	551	Ortlieb, Eva	205
Mostern, Ruth	499	Ortolja-Baird, Alexandra	458
Mourits, Rick	108	Osborne, Roger	392
Mpouli, Suzanne	59	Osenova, Petya	56
Mrugalski, Michał	125, 497	Osti, Giulia	556
Muck, Gaétan	561	Otty, Lisa	478
Mulliken, Jasmine Tiffany	33	Page, Kevin	65, 516
Mulliken, Jasmine	174	Page, Kevin R.	515, 559
Mun, Soo-Hyun	436	Pahor de Maiti, Kristina	56
Mundjar, Aleksander	221	Paklons, Eleonora	81
Murath, Antonia	461	Pallacci, Valentina	319
Murphy, Orla	90, 440	Palladino, Chiara	420
Murray, Padmini Ray	443	Paloposki, Hanna-Leena	91
Mussman, Ole	389	Pančur, Andrej	221, 586
Mäkelä, Eetu	150, 424	Paolanti, Marina	252, 383
Mühleder, Peter	206, 550	Papadopoulos, Costas	45, 195, 451
Müller-Laackman, Jonas	104	Papaki, Eliza	497
Münz-Manor, Ophir	71, 521	Parente Boavida, Clara	31, 585
Naether, Franziska	206, 550	Parigini, Margherita	406
Nagasaki, Kiyonori	51, 451, 453	Pascucci, Antonio	35
Naji, Jeneen	448	Pasqual, Valentina	283, 376, 393
Nakamura, Satoru	97, 144, 507	Pearlman, Nina	456
Nanni, Giacomo	409	Pedrazzini, Nilo	553
Nayyer, Kim	453	Pedretti, Carlo Teo	376
Neguera del Castillo, Darío	169	Pentzold, Christian	281
Nelson, David Ragnar	438	Pereira-Fariña, Martín	84
Netzer, Yael	378	Perna, Roberto	383
Neuber, Frederike	532	Peroni, Silvio	395, 446
Neuefeind, Claes	105, 270	Perraud, Alexandre	561
Niciński, Konrad Krzysztof	111	Pertsas, Vayianos	246
Nicka, Isabella	214	Petitpierre, Rémi	310, 354
Nicolaou, Anguelos	171, 508, 520	Petkovic, Ljudmila	566
Nicolosi, Dario	296	Petz, Cindarella	258
Niekler, Andreas	281, 357	Pham, Kim	147
Nielbo, Kristoffer	404	Pianzola, Federico	101
Nikolić, Dragana	511	Piasetzky, Eli	256
Ning, Cheng	130	Pica, Morgane	561
Nityananda, Vivek	485	Pichler, Axel	180
Nockels, Joe	254	Pickering, Victoria	455
Nomura, Nichole	461	Pidd, Mike	89
Norindr, Jade	349	Pielström, Steffen	25
Nowak, Krzysztof	596	Pierdicca, Roberto	252, 382
Noël, Geoffroy	45	Pikkanen, Ilona	91
Nunn, Christopher	26	Pikov, Nikita	575
Nunn, Christopher Alexander	185	Pimentel Trigo, Luís Manuel	109
Nurmikko-Fuller, Terhi	137	Ping Huang, Marianne	195
Nury, Elisa	468	Pirmann, Carrie	119
Nyhan, Julianne	456, 458	Pivovarova, Lidia	425
Nøklestad, Anders	533	Pluschkovits, Markus	176, 548

Pollin, Christopher	518	Rouquet, David	127, 552
Polomac, Vladimir	113	Rouxel, Lennart	527
Pořízka, Petr	513	Roy, Dibyadyuti	115, 443, 473
Prada Ziegler, Ismail	384	Ruiz Fabo, Pablo	59
Prats López, Montserrat	108	Rumyantzev, Maksim	575
Prell, Martin	471	Rusinek, Sinai	551
Priani Saiso, Ernesto	113, 574	Ryan, Yann Ciarán	425
Priego, Ernesto	596	Rybicki, Jan	261
Puren, Marie	266	Rykowska, Aleksandra	576
Pétermann, Stéphane	319	Ryu, Su-Rin	436
Pöckelmann, Marcus	429	Röttgermann, Julia	60
Rabaev, Irina	200	Saar, Ortal-Paz	275
Rabus, Achim	112	Sadek, Jawad	455
Raciti, Marco	497	Sagadin, Suzana	572
Radio, Erik	150	Sagi, Tomer	551
Radisch, Erik	486	Sahle, Patrick	106, 527
Raemy, Julien Antoine	515	Salgaro, Massimo	248
Rahman, Zead	279	Salvati, Benedetta	162
Rajan, Sai Sathiesh	78	Sander, Ruth	104
Rakityanskaya, Anna	573	Sander, Christoph	151
Rantala, Heikki	91	Sanderson, Robert	516
Rastas, Iiro	424	Schepp, Moritz	570
Rasterhoff, Claartje	45	Schimmenti, Andrea	376
Rastinger, Nina C.	228	Schindler, Jacqueline	529
Rau, Michael J.	481	Schmidt, Thomas	181
Raunig, Elisabeth	605	Schmidt, Katherine	402
Rebasti, Francesca	346	Schneider, Christa	384
Rebora, Simone	59, 191, 248	Schneider, Jonas	561
Rees, Arran	415	Schnober, Carsten	389
Reese, Griffith	553	Scholger, Walter	195
Reimann, Anna	38	Scholger, Martina	572
Reinöhl, Uta	105	Schreibman, Susan	195, 451
Renje, Elena	113	Schroeter, Julian	555
Renner, Max	602	Schubert, Zoe	592
Resch, Stefan	125, 497	Schuiki, Johannes	214
Reul, Christian	53	Schumacher, Mareike Katharina	71, 423, 525
Reza, Alia	274	Schuster, Christian	31, 585
Riaño Rupilanchas, Daniel	168	Schuster, Kristen	440
Riccardo, Katia	413	Schöch, Christof	25, 60, 497, 579, 581
Richards, Nina	245	Senatorova, Liza	464
Richards, Jennifer	485	Senotrusova, Polina	575
Ridge, Mia	92	Serif, Ina	38
Ripoll, Elodie	581	Šeļa, Artjoms	497
Ritter, Jörg	429	Shang, Wenyi	464
Rißler-Pipka, Nanette	446, 579	Shapland, Andrew	516
Rockenberger, Annika	51	Sharankov, Nicolay	107
Rockwell, Geoffrey	458	Shaw, Robert L. J.	359
Rodek, Ewa	598	Shibutani, Ayako	507
Roe, Glenn	154, 296, 566, 599	Shinozaki, Yuji	546
Roeder, Torsten	53, 567	Shipp, Kayla	516
Roemer, Thomas	256	Shtohryn, Tomash	567
Rojas Castro, Antonio	84, 260	Sichani, Anna-Maria	415
Romanello, Matteo	446	Siciliano, Angela	132
Romein, Annemieke	500	Siddiqui, Nabeel	64, 83
Romein, C. Annemieke	560	Silber-Varod, Vered	77
Rominger, Gian Duri	219	Simon, Rainer	184, 468
Ros, Ruben	199, 333	Singhal, Rashmi	277
Ros, Salvador	497	Sinisalu, Urmas	504
Rosenthaler, Lukas	148	Siqueira, Diego	466
Rosiński, Cezary	217, 535	Siwecka, Dorota	446
Rospoche, Marco	93	Skorinkin, Daniil	378, 513
Rosselli Del Turco, Roberto	589	Sloan, Kim	456
Rossenova, Lozana	592	Sluyter-Gäthje, Henny	293, 582
Rother, Lynn	338	Smith, Isabel	222

Smith, Olivia	485	Torabi, Katayoun	88
Smits, Thomas	81, 225, 240	Toth, Gabor Mihaly	385
Sober, Barak	256	Treusch, Pat	140
Sohmen, Lucia	592	Trilecke, Peer	293, 497, 513, 581
Solernou, Alaina	260	Trollip, Benito	453
Solernou Ferrer, Alaina	503	Truyen, Frederik	313
Sollazzo, Anna	211	Tsai, Richard Tzong-Han	362
Sopcak, Paul	248	Tscherne, Niklas	529
Sousa e Silva, Carlos Rogério	109	Tsui, Lik Hang	473
Sousa Garcia, Tiago	485	Tsutsumi, Tomoaki	603
Southammavong, Oudom	120	Tulai, Radu	314
Spadini, Elena	319, 398	Tuominen, Jouni	91
Stagg, Wyatt	547	Tupman, Charlotte	440
Stangl, Werner	233	Tóth-Czifra, Erzsébet	26, 497
Stebler, Andreas	561	Tögel, Philipp	471
Stefan, SaraGrace	160	Türkoglu, Enes	157
Steffes, Moritz	60	Uhl, Andreas	214
Stein, Christian	279	Ukolov, Dominik	79
Stein, Benno	357	Umerle, Tomasz	445, 535
Steiner, Christian	518	Underwood, Ted	110, 381, 464
Steward, Jeff	277	Uricchio, Tiberio	252, 382
Stiphout, Mees	531	Vaienti, Beatrice	310
Stojanovski, Jadranka	243	Valeonti, Foteini	455
Stoxreiter, Daniel	139	van Boeemen, Jelte	524
Stratil, Jasper	95	van Cranenburgh, Andreas	101
Straub, Alexandra	499	van Dalen-Oskam, Karina	99, 497
Streicher, Maria	527	van den Heede, Pieter	305
Streiter, Oliver	341	Van der Eecken, Paavo	227
Strull, Inbar	77	van der Lek-Ciudin, Iulianna	67
Stutzmann, Dominique	529	van der Plas, Luka	531
Störiko, Johanna Sophia	57	van der Ree, Michiel	101
Sutherland, Serenity	438	van der Sijs, Nicoline	500
Świetlik, Marta	307	Van der Stighelen, Katlijne	313
Szabo, Victoria	231	van Eijnatten, Joris	275
Szulińska, Agnieszka	224	Van Galen, Coen	108
Säily, Tanja	425	van Hage, Willem	389
Taban, Gökce	315	Van Kote, Elsa	349
Tadolti, Matteo	383	van Lange, Milan	305
Takeuchi, Ayano	234	van Lange, Milan Mikolaj	512
Tamrazyan, Hamest	289	van Nispen, Annelies	512
Tarpley, Bryan	88	van Oorschot, Frederike	185
Tasovac, Toma	iv, 37, 325, 497	van Oort, Thunnis	108
Teichmann, Lisa	353	van Rossum, Lisanne	497
Terracciano, Alda	455	van Zundert, Joris	389, 500
Terras, Melissa	254, 268, 328, 378, 443	VanderHart, Chanda	65, 137
Terrón, Grisel	260	Vasyutinsky Shapira, Daria	200
Terrón Quintero, Grisel	503	Vee, Annette	473
Tessier, Laurent	540	Veentjer, Ubbo	579
Thaisen, Jacob	533	Veldhoen, Sara	560
Thalken, Rosamond Elizabeth	539	Verbert, Katrien	313
Tharsen, Jeffrey	116, 466	Verreyen, Loren	236
Theron, Roberto	42	Vidal-Gorène, Chahan	207
Thiel, Marvin	357	Viehhauser, Gabriel	314
Thomas, Christian	583	Vieira Paulino, Joana	64
Thomsen, Mads R.	404	Vignoli, Michela	184
Tihonen, Iiro	424	Vilenchick, Dan	431
Tilton, Lauren	239, 453	Vipavc Brvar, Irena	31, 585
Tinits, Peeter	504	Visser, Noa	101
Tobalina-Pulido, Leticia	134, 586	Vitale, Valeria	468
Toker, Michael	521	Vitali, Fabio	376, 393
Tolonen, Mikko	425, 446	Vlachidis, Andreas	455
Tolstaya, Fekla	288	Vogeler, Georg	iii, 171, 387, 508, 520, 529
Tomasi, Francesca	202, 283, 376, 393, 395	Vogl, Malte	45, 118, 135, 466
Tonra, Justin	188, 440, 497	Volodin, Andrey	575

Wachek, Barbara	535	Yang, Xiaoyan	101
Wagner, Cosima	69	Yang, Zekun	542
Wagner, Travis	274	Yang, Huilin	543
Wahjoe, Muhammad Faiz	90	Yeh, Calvin	340
Walentynowicz, Wiktor	173	Yoffe, Gideon	256
Walkowiak, Tomasz	173	Yokoyama, Setsuko	78
Walsh, Melanie	463	Yousef, Tariq	194, 420
Walton, Jo Lindsay	478	Zaga, Moran	551
Wandl-Vogt, Eveline	42	Zalotyńska, Agnieszka Maria	111
Wang, Hao	370	Zardini, Stefania	415
Wang, Ruilin	425	Zbiral, David	359, 413
Wang, Jiajie	484	Zechner, Ingeborg	510
Warwick, Claire	159	Zeilinger, Florian	205
Watzinger, Alexander	245, 528	Zhan, Ya-qing	341
Webb, Sharon	448	Zhang, Jinbin	425
Weekley, Jeffrey	346	Zheng, Yuning	484
Wehner, Maximilian	53	Zhu, Benjun	473
Wehrheim, Lino	365	Zhu, Cuiping	482
Wei, Zhao	130	Ziegler, Theresa	578
Weigl, David M.	65, 138	Zúñiga, Jean-Paul	233
Weitin, Thomas	372		
Wermer-Colan, Alex	64		
Wermer-Colan, Henry Alexander	160		
Wessel, Ganzevoort	108		
Wessels, Bridgette	90		
Westbrook, John	291		
Westeel, Jeanne	120		
Westerling, Kalle	408, 553		
Wettlaufer, Jörg	58		
Wevers, Melvin	240		
Whittle, Sophie	90		
Wieczorek, Jan	217		
Wiegand, Frank	532		
Wiegmann, Matti	357		
Wijers, Martje	218		
Wiles, Simon	481		
Wilkens, Matthew	539		
Williams, Miranda	468		
Williamson, Magnus	485		
Wilson, Daniel C.S.	408		
Wilton, Demi-Mae	99		
Windhager, Florian	43		
Wingate, Alex	573		
Winko, Simone	301		
Wintermeier, Trent	29		
Winters, Jane	440		
Wintjes, Jorit	25		
Wisdom, Stella	597		
Witt, Andreas	418		
Witulski, Evan	480		
Wnuk, Magdalena	31, 307, 585		
Wolff, Christian	181		
Wolska, Magdalena	357		
Woods, Nathan D.	285		
Worm, Andrea	527		
Wrisley, David	69		
Wuttke, Ulrike	26		
Wübbena, Thorsten	488, 570		
Wünsche, Katharina	491		
Yakupova, Vera	232		
Yamada, Taizo	144, 507		
Yamada, Toshiyuki	507		
Yan, Jin	543		
Yang, Yuchen	86		

KARL-FRANZENS-UNIVERSITÄT GRAZ
GEISTESWISSENSCHAFTLICHE
FAKULTÄT

GALE

Digital Humanities Craft OG

DH 2023

Collaboration
as Opportunity